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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

OF ALCHEMISTS AND MAGICAL ARTS:
A NEW READING AND INTERPRETATION OF MANUSCRIPT
NO. 40 PRESERVED AT THE HISTORICAL ARCHIVE OF
MONTEMONACO¹

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1. Montemonaco and the legends of the Sibillini Mountain Range in the fifteenth century

There is a land in central Italy where illustrious legends seem to have elected to establish their mysterious abode, amid lofty peaks and precipitous ravines, in the very heart of the Apennines. For centuries and centuries visitors coming from all the regions of Europe have been directing their steps towards those sinister mountains, in search of the hidden realm of a prophesying Sibyl, living in her cave placed on a crowned cliff, or looking for a suitable place where to consecrate spellbooks and perform magical rituals, by a lake named after a most famous and controversial character of the Gospels, a prefect of Romanized Judaea who sentenced Jesus Christ to death.

The Sibillini Mountain Range hosted the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate, two celebrated sites lying just a few miles from one another: from the fourteenth century onwards, their fame has run the entire continent, with dozens and dozens of mentions retrieved in a plethora of literary works and geographical atlases, from the romance *Guerrino the Wretch* by Andrea da Barberino to Antoine de la Sale's account *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* up to the nineteenth- and twentieth-century investigations carried out on the two sites by scholars, researchers and scientists.

An interwoven world of fairy tales. Possibly, a far-more ancient myth, concealed beneath the later legendary layers which talk of a Sibyl and a Roman prefect. Legendary layers coming from other countries, not originally born here, and making up a superposition that lies over an inner core of tales, which precedes the epoch of Roman rule in the area and perhaps goes as far back as the Iron Age: forgotten tales possibly connected to earthquakes and the peculiar seismic character of the Sibillini Mountain Range, as we already outlined in our previous paper *The chthonian legend* (2020).

In previous articles belonging to the present series *The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend*, we highlighted the fact that the two main settlements involved in this fascinating legendary lore — out of their vantage position respectively set on the western and eastern side of the Sibillini Mountain Range — are Norcia, in today's Umbria province, and Montemonaco, in the region of Marche.

Fig. 1 - The small village of Montemonaco as it appears today (on the top of the picture the ascending slopes of Mount Sibyl)

In the present paper we intend to focus our attention on the small hamlet of Montemonaco, lying at the very foot of Mount Sibyl and explicitly mentioned by Antoine de la Sale in his fifteenth-century *Paradis*:

«This mountain is found in the Marca of Ancona in the territory of a castle whose name in Montemonaco, which means the mount of the monk. From this castle up to the the mount's summit, where the entrance to the cave is located, the distance is nine miles».

[In the original French text: «Le mont est es parties de la marque de Enconne et ou terrouer d'un chastel nommé monte moynaco, qui est autant a dire comme le mont du moyne. De cedit chastel jusques au plus hault du mont, ou l'entree de la cave est, on y compte ix milles»].

De la Sale's account is full of interesting details on the many small hamlets surrounding the main settlement of Montemonaco. «At the foot of the mountain, towards the peak of queen Sibyl, there is a village which is called Fougia» (in the original French text: «Au pié du mont, devers celui de la royne Sibile, a un villaige que l'on appelle Fougia...»): this is Foce,

still today an enchanting alpine location set right into the secluded glacial valley that is carved out between Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl. «And if you leave Montemonaco heading to Mount Sibyl you go past a village named Colino» (in the original French text: «Et au partir dudit chastel pour aler audit mont, voit on par un villaige nommé Colino»): the sparse clump of houses of Montemonaco's neighborhood of Collina still waits, today just as in the fifteenth century, for the steps of the visitors heading to the mystery of the Sibyl's Cave.

Fig. 2 - Montemonaco as mentioned in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 6v)

Fig. 3 - Montemonaco with its small hamlets of Collina and Foce as drawn in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 5v and 6r)

And Montemonaco was not a mere location for starting the climb to the Sibyl's top: the local residents actively took part in the day trips to the summit, helping the foreign visitors and going with them up to the magical cave, as recounted by de la Sale himself:

«I went there [to the Sibyl's Cave, editor's note] with a doctor of the said village, whose name was John of Sore; he led me there, together with other people of the hamlet of Montemonaco who escorted us up there, without doing nothing more».

[In the original French text: «j'etoie la alé avec un docteur dudit pais, nommé messire Jehan de Sore qui me conduisoit, et les gens de la ville de Montemoynac qui nous guidoient jusques la sans chose faire»].

Fig. 4 - Montemonaco and the supporting role of local inhabitants as described by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 10r)

We will later have a thorough chance to discuss this supporting role played by the inhabitants of Montemonaco with foreigners, as we will also find this same sort of information in the fifteenth-century manuscript retrieved in hamlet's historical municipal archive we are going to analyse in the present article.

It was Antoine de la Sale who definitely attached to Montemonaco its widespread, long-lasting fame as one of the main starting point — together with Norcia on the other side of the Sibillini Mountain Range — for visitors intending to reach the Sibyl's mountaintop and the notorious Cave which opened its gloomy jaws on that remote cliff.

However, we must note that at the mid of the fifteenth century, Montemonaco was already renowned for its role as an access point to the legendary mysteries of the Sibillini Mountain Range, even though the circulation of de la Sale's account was still very limited at the time (his visit to Mont Sibyl dates back to 1420, the manuscript containing his visit's account will be written some twenty years later only, and a printed version will be issued significantly later, in 1527).

Actually a subterranean current of rumours, hearsays and oral narratives had been already in place for long, if we consider that Antoine de la Sale, in 1420, could locally retrieve many tales about foreign visitors who had been visiting the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate in the preceding years; and we must also remember that the whole legendary lore concerning that territory, though hardly traceable in literary sources, was active and alive well before the fifteenth century, with limited signs of it which can be retrieved across the fourteenth in the works written by Petrus Berchorius and Fazio degli Uberti.

Certainly enough, in the late fifteenth century the eruption of celebrity of Mount Sibyl and its legendary queen will also be linked to the diffusion of Andrea da Barberino's romance *Guerrino the Wretch*, with its many printed editions. However, the subterranean circulation across Europe of information on the dark fame of Mount Sibyl, its cave and the nearby lake was already strong and thriving, especially amid men of letters and scholars.

This is attested by the famous letter written by Enea Silvio Piccolomini dated January, 15 1444, and following a specific enquiry submitted to him by «a prominent Saxon astronomer [...] the physician of the Duke of Saxony». At the time, the future Pope Pius II writes about *De Monte Veneris*, Norcia, and necromantic rituals carried out at a huge cavern and lake where «witches are found there and fiends and nocturnal wraiths; there those who house a bold heart can hear the voices of fiendish spirits, and talk to them and learn from them the magical arts» (in the original Latin text: «... striges esse et demones ac nocturnas umbras, ubi qui audaces animo sunt, spiritus nequam audiunt, alloquunturque et artes ediscunt magicas»). Montemonaco is not mentioned here, but we must remember that the two settlements, Norcia and Montemonaco, are closely associated to each other, lying on the opposite versants of the Sibillini Mountain

Range and joined by the 'Imperial Road', a main mountainous trail which crossed the high crests at the peak of Palazzo Borghese: an ancient track that connected the eastern and western sides of the Sibillini and just ran between the two sinister, notorious locations, the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate.

Fig. 5 - The southern area of the Sibillini Mountain Range with Norcia, Montemonaco and the elevated trail which ran between the two settlements

In that same year 1444 Felix Hemmerlin, in his work *De Nobilitate et Rusticitate Dialogus*, openly mentioned the area of the eastern side of the Sibillini Mountain Range, where Montemonaco lies, as the sinister Italian setting for the popular German legend of Tannhäuser, attracting impious visitors from abroad:

«It is said that not far from the town of Norcia and the castle of Montefortino [a small hamlet set three miles from Montemonaco, editor's note] lies Mount Sibyl [...] those cliffs are riddled with hollows and caves, which pierce the rock deep into the hidden core of the mountains through impracticable passages. This mount is known as Venusberg, because Venus, Vulcan's wife, makes it conjoined to fire [...] These subterranean chambers

harbour evil beings, fiendish spirits and demons, taking the shape of graceful maidens who beguile the men coming from foreign lands».

[In the original Latin text: «Et dicitur communiter mons Sibille coniunctus civitati Nursie et castello montifortino [...] et in eisdem montibus sunt cavernarum et speluncarum; et usque ad interiora montium pertuse concavitates et transitus meabiles; et in tantum quae ille dicit communiter mons veneris; ex eo quia put fertur Venus ultor vulcani venererii officii non sine calore perpetuo ibidem officiat [...] in hoc loco p nunc incubi sint et succubi et ipsus muliebris spei pulchritudine simulantes viros undecunquorum venerint largit indagates»].

Fig. 6 - The excerpt on the Sibyl, the Venusberg and Montefortino from the printed edition of Felix Hemmerlin's *De Nobilitate et Rusticitate Dialogus* (Strasbourg, 1500)

Another remarkable fifteenth-century mention concerning this same territory is retrieved in *Italia illustrata* (*Italy illustrated*), a work published by Flavio Biondo, an illustrious Italian historian, in 1453:

«On the highest peaks of the Apennines a castle named St. Mary in Gallo is found; nearby, in that same mountains, there is a huge cavern called 'the Sibyl's cave' by the populace. Further above, in the territory of Norcia, there is a lake where according to false rumours the waters would be replete of evil spirits rather than fish. The fame of both places has attracted - both in our present days and a lot more in past centuries, as is reported - a great number of people, interested in necromancy or in search of magical

wonders, up to those lofty mountains, with great exertion, and utterly in vain».

[In the original Latin text: «Summo in apenino est mons Sanctae Mariae in gallo oppidum cui ipso in apenino propinqua est caverna ingens sibillae vulgo appellata; et paulo superius est lacus ille in nursinorum agri apenino: quem vano ferunt mendacio piscium loco demonibus scaterere. Ea tamen duorum locorum fama multos diebus nostris et plures superioribus ut audivimus saeculis pellexit necromantia delectatos aut noscenda rerum mirandarum arduos hos montes magno vanoque labore conscenderent»].

Fig. 7 - Flavius Biondo's *Italy illustrated*, the excerpt on the Apennine Sibyl and demon's lake (manuscript Marston MS 35 preserved at the Beinecke Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Yale University, New Haven, CT, fifteenth century), folium 57r

Again, this literary reference points to Montemonaco and its surroundings: «St. Mary in Gallo» is today's Montegalloy, another small hamlet sitting a few miles from our main access point to the slopes of Mount Sibyl.

Fig. 8 - Montemonaco, Montefortino and Montegalloy sitting at the foot of the Sibillini Mountain Range and Mount Sibyl

As we can see, in the fifteenth century the whole eastern side of the Sibillini Mountain Range — Montemonaco, Montefortino, Montegalio — is considered by many different men of letters as an entryway to the magical realm of the Apennine Sibyl, in a close relation with the slopes of the enchanted mountain and the frightful cave that lies on the top of that crowned cliff.

The place was famous. The location was renowned. All across Europe. So much so that Antoine de la Sale himself wrote his narrative on Mount Sibyl urged, in the same years, by Agnes of Burgundy: in fact she owned a fine tapestry in her palace at Moulins-sur-Allier, the capital of the Duchy of Bourbon in central France.

And the tapestry, as reported by de la Sale, represented Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl, in central Italy:

«... because of this, my most illustrious dame, I send to you in writing and in portrait the mountain of the lake of Pilate and of the Sibyl, which are different from the way they are depicted in your tapestry; and also all I could see and get as information from the people living in that land...».

[In the original French text: «... pour ce, ma tresredoubtee dame, vous envoie par escript et pourtrait le mons du lac de Pilate et de la Sibille, qui autrement sont que en votre tapisserie ne sont faiz, et aussi tout ce que je ay peu veoir et moy informer par les gens du pais...»].

Fig. 9 - Agnes of Burgundy's tapestry as mentioned in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 1v)

Let's see, in the following paragraphs, what this European-wide renown meant for Montemonaco in the course of the fifteenth century.

2. Preaching against the dark renown: St. James of the Marches and Bernardino Bonavoglia of Foligno

The dark fame of Mount Sibyl and the Lake of Pilate, together with the close proximity of specific settlements (first and foremost Montemonaco and Norcia) to the two legendary sites, was perfectly known to the Church, especially to preaching friars of the time who were born and used to preach in that same areas, lying between Umbria and the Marches.

A most famous preacher and inquisitor of the fifteenth century, the Franciscan friar St. James of the Marches, could not dismiss the fiendish perils which seemed to overshadow this land, even though he did not leave in his writings any direct references to the Sibyl or Pilate. Nonetheless, he deliberately intended to highlight the peculiar character of Montemonaco as a place where self-styled necromancers seemed to reside and people came to ask for magical, impious services.

Let's consider his *Sermones dominicales*, a collection of sermons to be delivered in churches on Sundays, dating to the first half of the fifteenth century. We find them in various manuscripts, the most complete being Ms. 1 preserved at the Picene and Historical-Franciscan Library St. James of Marches in Falconara Marittima, written by the hand of the fifteenth-century preacher himself.

In the sermon *De sortilegiis (About wizardry)* the small hamlet sitting at the foot of Mount Sibyl is mentioned not once, but twice. In his first quote, St. James, as he reports examples of impious behaviours not to be imitated by the audiences of his sermons, narrates of a husband and a wife, who, craving to fulfill a special wish of theirs, made a deliberate trip from the Umbrian town of Spoletium to the Sibillini Mountain Range and Montemonaco, clearly being fully informed that that castle which lied close to Mount Sibyl was a most suitable location as to magic and witchcraft:

«Some do not ask God to have a child, they address the Fiend's spells instead, as I came to know in Spoletium. There was a couple who could not generate children, so they both went to mount The Monk to ask an enchanter. And, having cast the spell, the woman immediately got pregnant...».

[In the original Latin text: «Illa alia vadit non ad Deum pro habendis filiis, sed ad diabolum incantatorem, sicut inveni Spoleti. Cum coniuges non poterant habere filios, ambo venerunt ad montem Lumonacho ad incantatorem. Et facta incantatione, subito conceperunt filium...»].

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DOMINICA XL^e: DE SORTILEGIIS

Ille alter ut inveniat pecuniam et furta. Illa alia vadit non ad Deum pro habendis filiis, sed ad diabolum incantatorem, sicut inveni Spoleti. Cum coniuges non poterant habere filios, ambo venerunt ad montem Lumonacho ad incantatorem. Et facta incantatione, subito conceperunt filium. O mirabilis Deus! Quia postquam iste puer venit ad etatem unius anni cum dimidio ligabat sibi manum vel pedem vel colum ad columpnam et volebat se suffocare et dicebat puella sorori: trahe me cum fune per domum. Et dum habebat gladium volebat se percutere. Et habebat oculos quasi contaminatos, in etate quinque annorum, et nihil poterat discere et omnes libros lacerabat. Quem ego vidi oculis meis, considerans illud esse peccatum parentum.

Fig. 10 - A reference to Montemonaco contained in *De sortilegiis*, a sermon included in Iacobus de Marchia's fifteenth-century *Sermones Dominicales*, edited by Renato Lioi (Falconara Marittima, 1978), p.

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A second mention is presented a few pages ahead within the same sermon. In this further case, true demons are staged by St. James right in the outskirts of Montemonaco. The evil entities heal a sick man, in a typical effort, as the preacher explains, to deceive the poor and the needy, with the aim to stifle their faith in God:

«A young man came with an elderly person from the mountains to mount The Monk, and his leg was swollen like a barrel; for fifteen days the doctor could not improve his condition, so he was taken to an enchanter at a hermitage. All of a sudden he saw demons come to him and say: we are five demons of this rank, and they made a circle in the ground and cast a spell, and he was immediately healed. And the demons said to the good hermit who lived there: we cannot speak to you, because you have no faith in us».

[In the original Latin text: «iuvenis veniens cum sene de monte ad montem Lumonacho et inflata est crus quasi barile; et medicus per 15 dies nihil profecit sibi et dum portatus est ad incantatorem existentem in heremo, statim dum vidit eundem inceperunt demones dicere: nos sumus quinque demones in isto genu et facto circulo in terra et incantationem statim sanatis est. Et dixerunt cuidam bono viro ibi existenti: nos non possumus tibi dicere, quia non habes fidem in nobis».

et neque comedere, neque bibere valeo, neque dormire si non dixerō que ipse dixit. Ecce deceptio diabolica.

Item, iuvenis veniens cum sene de monte ad montem L u m o n a - c h o et inflata (!) est crus quasi barile; et medicus per 15 dies nihil profecit sibi et dum portatus est ad incantatorem existentem in heremo, statim dum vidit eundem inceperunt demones dicere: nos sumus quinque demones in isto genu et facto circulo in terra et incantationem (!) statim sanatus est. Et dixerunt cuidam bono viro ibi existenti: nos non possumus tibi dicere, quia non habes fidem in nobis.

Fig. 11 - A second mention of Montemonaco contained in *De sortilegiis*, a sermon included in Iacobus de Marchia's fifteenth-century *Sermones Dominicales*, edited by Renato Lioi (Falconara Marittima, 1978), p.

St. James was born in Monteprandone, a village of the Marches which is located not far from the Adriatic sea, but less than thirty miles from Mount Sibyl and the Lake of Pilate. Sure enough, the dark renown of the two mysterious sites, lying up there in the highlands and enshrouded in ancient legends, was perfectly known to him since his childhood (he himself recalls he had been a shepherd in his early youth); and, amid his many missions and journeys to various European countries as a preacher, inquisitor and papal legate, he repeatedly preached in his own homeland, travelling across

hamlets and castles in the territories of Ancona, Fermo, Macerata, Pesaro, Urbino and Ascoli Piceno. And including Montemonaco, too.

In his preaching against the legendary evil forces that supposedly were at work in the Sibillini Mountain Range, St. James of the Marches was not alone. Another Franciscan friar, in the course of that same fifteenth century, confronted in his sermons with the high cliffs of the mountains which raised between Norcia and Montemonaco.

Bernardino Bonavoglia of Foligno, a figure that is almost forgotten by historians and chroniclers, is remembered only for a printed edition of his Lent sermons (*Quintuplices sacrae quadragesimales inventiones*), published in Rome in 1606 and containing more than five hundred pages of guidance and examples for Christian preachers.

QVINTVPLICES
S A C R A E
QVADRAGESIMALES
INVENTIONES

R. P. F. Bernardini **BONA VOGLIA** Fulginatis,
Ord. Min. Obfer. sacrae Theol. Lecto. gene-
ralis, & Concionatoris praecleari.

*Quibus non solum quintuplex qualibet die varias componen-
di Conciones modus ostenditur, verum etiam quintu-
plex sub graui, & eleganti Inuentione
Concio in praxi proponitur.*

Opus Euangelicis Concionatoribus, propter Inuentiones ipsas,
ordinem singularem, sacrae Scripturae inductiones praeci-
puas, SS. PP. doctrinas, ac tandem motiua, erudi-
tione plena, vel in primis desiderabile.

C V M P R I V I L E G I O .

ROMAE, Apud Heredes Aloisij Zannetti.
M. DC. VI.

SVPERIORVM PERMISSV.

Fig. 12 - Bernardino Bonavoglia of Foligno, *Quintuplices sacrae quadragesimales inventiones* (Rome, 1606)

But there is something more to it. In 1888, a scholar from the Umbrian town of Foligno, Michele Faloci Pulignani, retrieved an ancient manuscript at the Municipal Library of the same town, of which he was the director.

Pulignani, who announced its find in the journal *Miscellanea Francescana*, also directed by him, reported that the fifteenth-century document, catalogued as AH II 10, included 62 sermons written by Friar Bernardino Bonavoglia.

It's Faloci Pulignani himself who remarks that «the oratorical works of the old preachers», including those written in the fifteenth century by «St. James of Marches, St. Bernardino of Siena» and others, «truly must be considered as unexplored treasures full of documents of the highest import on the customs and opinions of that age».

For sure, Bernardino Bonavoglia does not match the outstanding preaching qualities and effectiveness reached by St. James of Marches, with his knowledgeable mixture of biblical quotes and real-life examples: Pulignani notes that Bonavoglia's eloquence «shows up only here and there», and «often is soon replaced by the subtleties of the Scholastic approach, which predominates across the whole huge volume».

Fig. 13 - The article written by Michele Faloci Pulignani on the finding of a manuscript containing sermons by Bernardino Bonavoglia (*Miscellanea Francescana di storia, di lettere, di arti*, Vol. III, Fasc. III, Foligno, 1888), p. 65

But the sermons contain «so many tales, classical reminiscences, pious legends, popular opinions, italian and latin verses» that the risk of a «boring, verbose» narrative is, at least according to Faloci Pulignani, utterly eluded.

Amid this plethora of tales, Friar Bernardino Bonavoglia could not omit to mention a legend which lived not far from his own hometown, Foligno, as recorded by Faloci Pulignani himself:

«... And, as to superstitions, of great interest is the excerpt in which he [Bernardino Bonavoglia, editor's note] [...] reports about the grave of Pilate in the neighborhood of Norcia...».

discrimini (2). Una volta ricorda che a tempo di S. Giacomo della Marca fu bruciata in Perugia una certa Santuccia da Gualdo, maliarda famosa che confessò aver ucciso molti bambini (3). Ed a proposito di superstizioni, è interessantissimo il brano nel quale riferisce i ritornelli soliti ad usare per liberarsi da certi mali (4), e quello dove parla del sepolcro di Pilato presso Norcia, e di alcune discordie civili sorte in Ascoli, nel qual racconta parla del b. Sabino da Campello ecc. (5). E del nominato San Giacomo della Marca parla più volte, per esempio, ricordando un fatto accaduto in Ungheria (6), un processo fatto a Roma (7) ecc.

Fig. 14 - Michele Faloci Pulignani on Bernardino Bonavoglia's excerpt concerning the Lake of Pilate
(*Miscellanea Franceseana di storia, di lettere, di arti*, Vol. III, Fasc. III, Foligno, 1888), p. 66

And so one of the sermons, *De superstitionibus*, includes a lively tale of what used to happen, in the fifteenth century, at the Lake of Pilate, up there within the high cliffs of Mount Vettore.

Can we read this portion of the sermon? Unfortunately, today the original manuscript mentioned by Faloci Pulignani in 1888 and containing the sermons of Bernardino Bonavoglia, labelled under the old coding 'AH II 10', cannot be retrieved anymore in the collection currently preserved at the Municipal Library *Dante Alighieri* in Foligno. Under your author's impulse, at the date of the publication of the present paper the personnel of the Library, after thoroughly searching across the collection in an attempt to recover the volume, officially provided the information that the manuscript is not to be found anywhere in their collection. Actually it might have gone

lost, or might even have been stolen (it seems that the same Faloci Pulignani was marked by a bad track record concerning book-stealing aimed at feeding his own personal collection of ancient books...)

Luckily enough, in 1893, Arturo Graf, an Italian man of letters and professor at the University of Turin, while editing his *Miti, leggende e superstizioni del medioevo* (*Myths, legends and superstitions of the Middle Ages*) was informed by Faloci Pulignani of the existence of the recently-retrieved manuscript that contained sermons elaborated by Bernardino Bonavoglia. As Graf was preparing his essay on *A mountain of Pilate in Italy*, for inclusion in his new book, he asked the man of letter from Foligno to kindly provide him with a copy of the relevant text: «I owe this excerpt to the kindness of Michele Faloci Pulignani, who drew it from a manuscript dating to the fifteenth century...», wrote Graf.

ARTURO GRAF
MITI, LEGGENDE E SUPERSTIZIONI
DEL
MEDIO EVO

VOLUME II.
LA LEGGENDA DI UN PONTEFICE
DEMONOLOGIA DI DANTE - UN MONTE DI PILATO IN ITALIA
FU SUPERSTIZIOSO IL BOCCACCIO?
SAN GIULIANO NEL "DECAMERONE" E ALTROVE
IL RIFIUTO DI CELESTINO V - LA LEGGENDA DI UN FILOSOFO
ARTÙ NELL'ETNA - UN MITO GEOGRAFICO

nostro officio predicatori. — Debbo comunicazione di questo testo alla cortesia di Michele Faloci Pulignani, che lo trasse da un manoscritto del secolo XV, contenente prediche di fra Bernardino, e conservato sotto la segnatura AH, II, 10 nella Comunale di Foligno.

TORINO
ERMANN O LOESCHER
FIRENZE — ROMA
Via Tornabuoni, 20 — Via del Corso, 307
1893

Fig. 15 - Arturo Graf's reference to Michele Faloci Pulignani and the sermons by Bernardino Bonavoglia, from his book *Miti, leggende e superstizioni del medioevo* (Turin, 1893), p. 163

So let's read from Arturo Graf's book, in which the full Latin text on the Lake of Pilate, as drawn from the preacher's manuscripted sermon *De superstitionibus*, can be thoroughly perused.

To begin with, Bernardino Bonavoglia totally confirms the rumors about the legendary tale concerning Pontius Pilate and his final resting place set amid the Sibillini Mountain Range:

«People say that in the vicinity of Norcia there is a mountain, in which a lake named after Pilate stands; many hold the opinion that the prefect's dead body was brought by the demons up to those waters on a chariot drawn by bulls».

[In the original Latin text: «Dicitur autem quod iuxta Nursiam est quidam mons in quo est lacus qui dicitur Pilati, quia opinio est quasi multorum, illuc corpus eius fuisse a dyabolis per tauros in vehiculo deportatum»].

This is the same legend referred by Antoine de la Sale in his *The paradise of Queen Sibyl*: a tale which is rooted in ancient narratives concerning the final destination of the cursed corpse of Pontius Pilate, dating back to the High Middle Ages, as illustrated in our previous paper *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*.

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* * Dicitur autem quod iuxta Nursiam est quidam mons in quo est lacus qui dicitur Pilati, quia opinio est quasi multorum, illuc corpus eius fuisse a dyabolis per tauros in vehiculo deportatum. Ad hunc locum veniunt homines diabolici de pro-

Fig. 16 - Norcia and the Lake of Pilate as mentioned by Bernardino Bonavoglia, from Arturo Graf's *Miti, leggende e superstizioni del medioevo* (Turin, 1893), p. 163

As we found previously in Antoine de la Sale, Enea Silvio Piccolomini, Felix Hemmerlin and Flavio Biondo, according to Bernardino Bonavoglia, too, wizards and enchanters from around Europe seem to know well the place and its wondrous, fiendish character:

«To that place evil men flock from both close and far-away territories...»

[In the original Latin text: «Ad hunc locum veniunt homines diabolici de propinquis et remotis partibus...»].

But what happens at the lake? What sort of rituals are put on stage, up there? The lively description provided by the fifteenth-century friar, for the thrill and repentance of his frightened audiences, sheds a shadowy, sinister light on the necromantic ceremonies that people coming from abroad staged by the icy waters of the lake concealed amid the high crests of Mount Vettore, in an isolated, scary setting in which human voices and impious summonings resounded dreadfully at the ears of those same self-styled, would-be enchanters:

«... and they make there altars with three circles; then they set themselves with an offer within the third circle, and summon the demon with the specific name they wish, by reading from a book that they want to consecrate to the Fiend».

[In the original Latin text: «... et faciunt ibi aras cum tribus circulis, et ponentes se cum oblatione in tertio circulo, vocant demonem nomine quem volunt, legendo librum consecrandum a dyabulo»].

portatum. Ad hunc locum veniunt homines diabolici de propinquis et remotis partibus, et faciunt ibi aras cum tribus circulis, et ponentes se cum oblatione in tertio circulo, vocant demonem nomine quem volunt, legendo librum consecrandum a dyabulo. Qui veniens cum magno strepitu et clamore dicit: Cur me queris? Respondet: Volo hunc librum consecrare, idest volo ut tenearis facere omnia que in ipso scripta sunt quoties te invocavero, et pro labore tuo dabo animam meam. Et sic firmato pacto accipit librum dyabolus, et designat in eo quosdam characteres, et deinceps legendo librum dyabolus promptus est ad omnia mala faciendum. Ecce qualiter captivantur illi miseri et dampnati homines. Semel accidit quod quidam, dum vellet

Fig. 17 - Summoning at the Lake of Pilate according to Bernardino Bonavoglia, from Arturo Graf's *Miti, leggende e superstizioni del medioevo* (Turin, 1893), p. 163

Up to this point we are still retracing the truth of actual facts, as there is no doubt that people really used to come to the Lake of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave to perform magical, prohibited arts. Nonetheless, as to the next phases, we cannot but recollect what Flavio Biondo, and many others, wrote about all those simpletons who liked to consider themselves as real sorcerers: nothing happened, and they just used to take their way back

home down the mountain's slopes to their complete scorn, after having proceeded to the highest peaks «with great exertion, and utterly in vain».

Instead, in Bernardino Bonavoglia's narrative, which was designed to scare his listeners in churches and ensure they would never attempt at committing such major, unforgivable sin, demons do show up and a ghastly deal is cut:

«He [the demon] comes with frightful noise and uproar and says: 'Why did you summon me?' And the answer is: 'I want to consecrate this spellbook, namely I want you to do for me all the things that are written in it, everytime I conjure you up; and for your services I will deliver to you my soul'. So the contract is signed; the demon takes the book and marks some characters in it: from now on, if the book is read the demon is ready to carry out any sort of evil. And here is how those wretched, cursed men are subjugated».

[In the original Latin text: «Qui veniens cum magno strepitu et clamore dicit: Cur me queris? Respondet: Volo hunc librum consecrare, idest volo ut tenearis facere omnia que in ipso scripta sunt quoties te invocavero, et pro labore tuo dabo animam meam. Et sic firmato pacto accipit librum dyabolus, et designat in eo quosdam characteres, et deinceps legendo librum dyabolus promptus est ad omnia mala faciendum. Ecce qualiter captivantur illi miseri et dampnati homines»].

But the whole matter, warns Bernardino Bonavoglia, is far from safe. Accidents may happen in the course, and they are not pleasant at all:

«Once it occurred that an enchanter, wishing to consecrate his book in the way we described above, standing within the readied circle, conjured a certain demon; but he was told that the fiendish creature was not present there at the lake, as he had gone to the town of Ascoli instead [17 miles from the Lake of Pilate and 12 miles from Montemonaco, editor's note]».

[In the original Latin text: «Semel accidit quod quidam, dum vellet modo predicto consecrare librum, stans in circulo ibi ordinato, vocavit quendam demonem, cui datum responsum ibi non adesse, sed ivisse ad civitatem Asculi»].

In Ascoli the demon dedicated himself to the slaughtering of a huge number of citizens, by adding that as soon as he completed his work there he would be back to fulfil the enchanter's wishes.

Of course, as narrated by Bernardino, when the poor enchanter found out that the massacre in the town had occurred for real, «solemnly declared to dismiss all magical arts and spells, because he finally got that the art of the Fiend in enslaving souls and losing them forever is much more powerful» (in the original Latin text: «statuit firmiter superdictus vir... dimittere artem magicam et incantationum, considerans magnam esse artem in dyabulo ad animas capiendas atque perdendas»).

So in the fifteenth century the Church, and the preachers who used to run central Italy to deliver their sermons to the peasants across the towns, villages and hamlets lying around the Sibillini Mountain Range, were fully aware that the elevated peaks of the Apennines in that specific area were at the center of a wicked, unholy attention, which attracted people from foreign countries as far as those remote locations in search of fiendish intercourses; and they knew, too, that a small settlement such as Montemonaco, so dangerously close to the notorious Cave and Lake, hosted in town and in the nearby elevations soi-disant enchanters and equivocal hermits who maintained they could establish forbidden contacts with mighty demons.

All this was enough to keep the civil and ecclesiastical authorities on the watch for potential troubles on any kind, with special reference to foreigners possibly carrying out prohibited activities on the mountaintops, and even, perhaps, with the help of the locals.

We will see, in the next paragraphs, that this is exactly what used to happen commonly and repeatedly, especially in summers, and especially in Montemonaco. With a lot of help and support from the villagers.

This support was not provided by the locals out of any specific passion for demons, spellbooks and other dark, supernatural mysteries.

Their drive was far more earthly. As we will discover in the next sections of the present article.

3. A story of demons, summonings and bargains: manuscript no. 40 at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco

Montemonaco: a tiny, remote village lost amid the slopes of the Apennines at the very center of the Italian peninsula, known amid a milieu of learned persons, adventurers, self-styled magicians and soi-disant enchanters as the entrypoint to a region of dark, sinister legends, where a Sibyl lived a lascivious, concealed life within a subterranean realm and a lake inhabited by demons could be a most suitable place to consecrate magical, powerful spellbooks.

And of this fame, in addition to the references we illustrated in the previous paragraphs, we find another astounding trace in a manuscript retrieved, not long ago, in Montemonaco itself: an amazing witness of the peculiar renown enjoyed by this mountainous hamlet in the course of the fifteenth century. Its perusal will open to us a new insight on what this fame meant for Montemonaco at the time, shedding an interesting light on the sort of relationship that happened to take shape between the visitors coming from abroad — eager to meet the thrill and vibe of the legendary tales they were craving to address — and local residents, who well knew both their imposing mountains and the ardent expectations of their 'customers', who in summers flocked to their otherwise placid, peaceful village.

This manuscript is preserved at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco. And it is a precious, illuminating trove, as we will see in the next paragraphs.

3.1 An unexpected trove

Our story begins at the end of the 1990s. It is the year 1997 and an astounding manuscripted document, dating back to the fifteenth century and totally unknown up to that very moment, is found and published the next year in Montemonaco.

It is a single folium. Its rear side bears the following text, possibly written a couple of centuries later:

«Manuscript no. 40, 1442, June 12th.. Acquittal rendered by the Apostolic Curia of the March of Ancona as to spiritual cases in favor of the Priors of the Municipality and the people of the land of Monte Monaco for having supported and accommodated men of wicked life, or, more precisely, with the use of a more common word, Sorcerers in their land of Monte Monaco. Attested by Victorinus of Santa Vittoria, notary public».

[In the original Latin text: «n. 40, 1442, 12 Iunii. Sententia absolutionis Curie Apostolice in Marchia Anconitana in spiritualibus favore Priorum Comunitatis et hominum terrae Montis Monaci de favendo et recipiendo homines pravae vite, aut melius dicam, comuni vocabulo Magos accusatorum in eorum terra Montis Monaci. Rogavit Victorinus de Santa Vittoria notarius»].

As we will see later in the following paragraphs, this later introductory note includes two errors (the correct document's date is June 15, 1452, and the court is not the Apostolic Curia, which is in Rome, but the local General Curia of the Marches). However, the manuscript seems to contain information of the utmost relevance for our search on the legends of the Sibillini Mountain Range in the fifteenth century.

Actually this document was written in the same century of the references provided by Antoine de la Sale, Enea Silvio Piccolomini, Felix Hemmerlin, Flavio Biondo, and the preachers St. James of the Marches and Bernardino Bonavoglia of Foligno.

Has this manuscript, which refers to the presence of sorcerers in Montemonaco, anything to do with the Sibyl's Cave, the Lake of Pilate and their dark legends? Is this document a further proof of the worried attention devoted by the Church to the unwanted concourse of enchanters that seemed to plague the remote hamlet of Montemonaco?

We will soon see that the answer is in the affirmative. The Apennine Sibyl and Pontius Pilate are there, with their load of unholy mystery.

But, before proceeding into a detailed perusal of the manuscript, let's briefly retrace the peculiar story of this wondrous finding and, subsequently, provide a bit of information on the historical milieu which lies at the background of what is recounted in the ancient folium.

102 1447 10 Junii

Sententia adulationis Curie
Aptie in Marchia Anconitana
in spiritualibus favore Romanorum
Comunitatis et hominum terrarum
Montis Mariani de iurando
et recipiendo homines pro
vite aut melius dicitur comuni
vocabulo Magis acceptorum
in coram Curia Montis Mariani
Magister Antonius de h. Nello
vra Nobis

San. Antonius de h. Nello

Fig. 18 - Manuscript no. 40 preserved at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco (single folium, verso), from Progetto Elissa, *Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.* (Montemonaco, 1998), p. 31

Throughout the present paper we will be using the only images of manuscript no. 40 which are currently available for research purposes in the public domain, as published by Editrice Miriamica - Project Elissa in the booklet *Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.* (1998), p. 13 (recto) and p. 31 (verso). Unfortunately these pictures were released in low resolution only. Before completing the present article, your author submitted an enquiry to the municipality of Montemonaco kindly asking for a higher-resolution image; however, the administration has not yet provided the requested files, owing to scanning issues linked to the bad conservation conditions of the parchment sheet, which underwent further degradation following the 2016 earthquake sequence in central Italy. In case of future availability of the requested images, an updated version of the present article will be promptly released with the inclusion of more detailed pictures.

3.2 Project Elissa: reviving the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range

Unbelievable as it may seem, manuscript no. 40 had been sleeping its sound sleep in the archives of the municipality of Montemonaco for nearly five hundred fifty years, totally undisturbed, amid an equally dormant collection of «fifty other, far-less-interesting manuscripts», as Anna Maria Piscitelli recounts in her book *Antoine De La Sale - Viaggio nei misteri della Sibilla* (1999).

Nobody had ever noticed that significant piece of documentation, with the exception of some unnamed seventeenth- or eighteenth-century archivist who wrote that number — «40» — and a few imprecise words on the back of the parchment sheet. Not even in modern and contemporary times, when the debate concerning an Apennine Sibyl has been attracting the attention and interest of researchers from different parts of the world, nobody in Montemonaco had ever thought of rummaging amid the collection of ancient manuscripts preserved in town, just to check whether anything interesting might be found.

An external hand was required. And that hand was brought in Montemonaco by Anna Maria Piscitelli.

Anna Maria Piscitelli was the founder of 'Elissa', a cultural project which from 1995 to 2007 intended to proactively confront with the mysterious, fascinating figure of the Apennine Sibyl with the support of a number of researchers operating in different disciplines. With the establishment of their headquarters right in Montemonaco, Piscitelli and the project brought new life and freshness to an investigation that was substantially languishing following the excavations carried out on the top of Mount Sibyl in the 1950s, urging local authorities to pay increased attention to a matter which was to be considered as an illustrious heritage belonging to all the people who lived in the area.

Fig. 19 - Project Elissa's headquarters in Montemonaco, Via Italia 16

With four large conferences held in Spoleto (*Il nascondiglio divino - Cultura sibillina e centri oracolari*, 1996; for the conference proceedings: *Sibilla Appenninica - I volti di pietra della matriarchia*, Editrice Miriamica, 1997), and then in Ascoli Piceno and Montemonaco (*Le terre della Sibilla Appenninica - Antico crocevia di idee scienze e cultura*, 1998; *Errante erotica eretica - L'icona Sibillina fra Cecco d'Ascoli e Osvaldo Licini*, 1999), and finally in Amandola (*Sibilla sciamana della Montagna e la grotta appenninica*, 2000), Project Elissa succeeded in attracting new energies from both the academic world and local institutions, recovering

financial funding to conduct new studies, activities and prospections in the neglected domain of the Apennine Sibyl's legendary tale.

Fig. 20 - Publications on the Apennine Sibyl released by Project Elissa

The greatest achievement of Project Elissa was the performance, in the year 2000, of a new, fully-authorised, investor-supported round of scientific investigation on the cliff of Mount Sibyl, in search of the lost subterranean hollows: a geognostic survey based on a ground-penetrating radar. The high-frequency electromagnetic pulses, as reflected by the subterranean masses of rock, unveiled, according to the geological report edited by Angelo Beano, «multiple radar echoes [...]. And the correlation between the topographic profile of the electromagnetic disturbances and the geological patterns as measured during the survey carried out at ground level, fosters speculations that a number of hollows may actually exist beneath the peak's surface».

To this outstanding achievement, we must also add the trove of manuscript no. 40 at the historical archive of Montemonaco: a brilliant finding that would have been subject to a further delay for who knows how many decades more, in the absence of a praiseworthy Project Elissa and considering the unbelievable inaction and passivity maintained by the municipality itself up to that moment.

But what happened to Project Elissa after more than ten years of effective, rewarding activities? What results did they attain? And how close did they get to a true, meaningful, pregnant interpretation of the whole sibilline matter?

Fig. 21 - Three-dimensional view of the peak of Mount Sibyl with the position of the geoelectric anomalies (from *Indagine geofisica* by Angelo Beano, paper included in *Sibilla sciamana della Montagna e la grotta appenninica*, Montemonaco, 2001, p. 196-197)

Following a long season of cooperation with major local institutions and support by a number of academics and researchers, eventually the project's momentum ground to a halt. And, in 2007, its headquarters in Montemonaco were ultimately shut down.

Actually, throughout its life, Project Elissa had to confront with a growing opposition. Already in the volume *Errante erotica eretica - L'icona Sibillina fra Cecco d'Ascoli e Osvaldo Licini* (Montemonaco, 2000) Anna Maria Piscitelli felt the need to criticize «the residual, biased suspicions of some [...] and] the indifference of others towards our well-established cultural project». And the subsequent year, in the volume *Sibilla sciamana*

della Montagna e la grotta appenninica, we find open mentions to the «annoyance» that the activities carried out in Montemonaco would raise, according to some, amid the local residents, with a reference to the National Park of the Sibillini Mountain Range which would allegedly consider the ongoing cultural initiatives concerning the research on the Apennine Sibyl as «dangerous and unsettling» for the people living in the area.

In the same volume, Anna Maria Piscitelli, in a bitter tone, notes that «still today the local populations feel the ancestral connection with their traditions almost as a shame, which they would gladly get rid of», with unacceptable «charges of heresy and unholiness», especially when new research activities on the Sibyl are promoted «by someone, namely a woman, not even born here but transplanted in the area».

What was the matter with all that? We will see it in the next paragraph.

3.3 Project Elissa's 'original sin'

In the very end, the traditional short-sighted, narrow-minded closure of the local institutions in the Sibillini Mountain Range area — and Piscitelli effectively depicts this sort of approach with the words «a National Park in which they actively operate for the reintroduction of the chamois and the bear [...] to show everyone how good they are and how much they love nature [...] at the same time leaving a historical site known all over the world to the condition of a heap of unstable rubble and broken debris, not different from an illegal garbage dump» — the diffidence of the locals towards any activities not immediately marked by the urge of business, trade and money-making, just collided with the peculiar original character of Project Elissa and its promoters, too distant from anything the people in Montemonaco and neighborhood could never understand and, eventually, share.

At the mid of the 1990s, Anna Maria Piscitelli already came out from a long track in the hermetic tradition of ancient Egyptian origin, a mythically-revealed discipline in theology, philosophy, astrology, alchemy, esoterism and the occult. Since 1985 Piscitelli had been the heir of the teachings of

Ciro Formisano, also known as Giuliano Kremmerz, a scholar who, between the nineteenth and twentieth century, had been re-discovering the tradition of classical Hermeticism as transferred in the land of Italy in past centuries. So, while promoting the new course of reasearch on the Apennine Sibyl we described above, she was also the leader of the Schola Philosophica Hermetica Classica Italica - Fratellanza Terapeutica Magica di Miriam, a brotherhood which may remind of Freemasonry and that established a direct connection with Kremmerz's teachings with relation to spiritual and material healing effected at a distance through magical influence.

Fig. 22 - A work on hermeticism and magical healing written by Giuliano Kremmerz and published in 1929

Of course, owing to the strong pagan-like flavour of all this, the activities carried out in Montemonaco by Project Elissa did raise more than a mere suspicion, especially amid the catholic environment.

But the main 'original sin' of Project Elissa was not its heathenish lineage including Hermeticism and ancient cults (all in all, the Apennine Sibyl may appear to have possible link with potential initiatic traditions lost in the mists of time).

The 'sin' at the very foundation of the project's action was of a theoretical sort.

We must note that a key point in Giuliano Kremmerz's teachings was the concept of 'Matriarchy': a symbolic principle which expresses the origin of universal life, a cosmical womb or matrix, a supreme generative force marked by kindness and spiritual beauty. A divine foundation concealed behind our visible world.

If we add to this the «personal research» carried out by Piscitelli — as she herself reports in *Sibilla sciamana della Montagna e la grotta appenninica* — «as a former supporter of women's rights in the 1968 [...] up to the discovery of an unbroken link which, since time immemorial, demonstrated the true historical reality of a single feminine archetype», we fall right into the idea of an Apennine Sibyl as a most illustrious expression of a powerful, benign, creative principle operating in and across nature, a sort of superior goddess embodying the cosmical cycles of life, death and regeneration.

But this is not enough. Because Anna Maria Piscitelli was also strongly influenced by the vision mainly supported by the Italian writer, poet, insurgent fighter against the Nazi troops and activist Joyce Lussu.

We had the occasion, in other papers, to strongly criticize the unfounded, fanciful beliefs held by this passionate, heroic, multifaceted figure, and concerning the alleged, unproven existence of a primigenial gynocentric society, situated in a sort of ancient, mythical Golden Age, ruled by women and opposed to war, subsequently defeated and replaced throughout Europe by a male-dominated, warlike culture, according to an unproven model proposed by Lithuanian archaeologist Marija Gimbutas in 1991; a model fabulously applied by Lussu — in the total absence of any scientific and historical confirmation — to the figure of the Apennine Sibyl, turned into a sort of positive, feminist, protective oracle and depicted as a benign character in close relation with the local communities of women, teaching arts and crafts to the villagers and promoting peace as a memory of the ancestral societies living in peace under female control.

As recounted by Piscitelli herself in *Sibilla sciamana della Montagna*, «a crucial element [in my personal research, editor's note] also was the encounter with Joyce Lussu, which occurred at the end of the 1980s, and especially with her book *Il libro perogno*». This was a book in which Lussu included her most whimsical, extravagant statements on the Apennine Sibyl, a portrait remarkably distorted by the social and political inclination of the writer and activist, who devoted herself to manifold battles in favor of women's empowerment.

Fig. 23 - Joyce Lussu's *Il libro perogno - Su donne, streghe e sibille* (Ancona, 1982)

Charismatic as she was, her gaze almost magnetic and her voice firm and steady, Joyce Lussu vehemently explained to Piscitelli her groundless assumptions: «she began to talk to me of the civilization which is called by the archeologists 'Danubian', and extended from Ukraine to Spain and as far as our Italian lands, taking on the characters of 'apennine' or 'sibilline', and giving life to an industrious, peaceful society open to trade and cultural exchanges [...] The role of women, who preserved all the memories useful for the wellness of communities, was primary there, so much so that the wisest among them [...] handed those memories over to the youngest and most proficient in learning. So - she said - the Sibyls were born, they

preserved the knowledge, the habits, the traditions of this most ancient civilization. Subsequently [...] a single figure of Sibyl, as an oracle of our mountains, came out...».

This historical nonsense was accompanied, as usual in Joyce Lussu's thought, by concepts such as the later marginalization of the Sibyl and her «confinement in the esoterical domain and the trivial magic, in superstition fostered by ignorance, in the process of demonization carried out by the great inquisitors of the fifteenth century».

With her capturing, mesmerizing eyes, Lussu, at the time in her late years, pushed herself as far as to bestow on young Piscitelli the fateful task of restoring the Sibyl to the true role she deserved, beyond the oblivion she had been sentenced to by men.

Here the damage was done. Because foolish statements prove not truer when they are uttered with firmer voice or steadier gaze, even if the voice and blue-eyed gaze are those of a prominent figure of our times, such as Joyce Lussu.

Fig. 24 - Joyce Lussu in her elderly years

And so, from that moment onwards, Piscitelli's mission became «to outline the figure of the Apennine Sibyl from the many superimposed layers which

have labelled her as a mere oracle, an almost extraneous woman, but subject to male rule, with the aim to reinstate her in her dignity and self-empowerment»: a programme that would nicely fit a women's liberation group.

From this to «the assimilation of Mount Sibyl to the concept of Matriarchy» (*Sibilla Appenninica - I volti di pietra della matriarchia*, 1997), and then to «the existence of an oral tradition preserved, handled and handed over from women to women and from mother to daughter over the secrets of life [...] of which such women were aware in their role as 'Virgin Sibyls'» (*Le terre della Sibilla Appenninica - Antico crocevia di idee scienze e cultura*, 1998), the path for Project Elissa was fancifully marked and even doomed to failure, with imaginative outcomes such as the chance to «assume for the apennine Sibyl the role of 'curandera' [traditional healer, editor's note] of the Sibillini Mountain Range, considering the influence that she has had in a persisting tradition oriented at the sciences of nature and healing, phytotherapy practices, popular and empirical, in the area of the Sibillini Mountains» (*Sibilla sciamana della Montagna e la grotta appenninica*, 2000).

As we already had the possibility to point out in previous papers (*The chthonian legend, Four years from 'The chthonian legend'*), there is no match at all between Lussu's and Piscitelli's Apennine Sibyl and the documented tradition which narrates of a Sibyl inhabiting the Sibillini Mountain Range.

The legendary figure of the Sibyl of the Apennines, and the sites where the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate lie, are all marked, since the earliest literary witnesses available to us, by a fully dark hue, with a demonic presence at both places, necromancy being carried out by the Cave and Lake, and a blood-curdling otherworldly character for the two geographical features which are the landmarks for the legend. No space nor any plausible evidence exist for any alleged sisterhood of 'sibyls' scattered among the Neolithic villages in the Sibillini Mountain Range area. In all available sources, there is no joyful image of a friendly, pacifist Sibyl dispensing wise counsels to local women.

There has never been such thing as a 'good' Sibyl: the two legends — Sibyl's and Pilate's — are both dark and fearful and 'bad', as philology

clearly shows. And as the two sites themselves — a gloomy cavern on a mountaintop and a ghastly lake set amid precipitous cliffs — clearly suggest their patent role as sinister settings for the two legendary tales.

The reason for that is that both legends are probably rooted in a same appalling background, leaving no space for kindness, gentle women and nice artistic crafts: earthquakes, as we conjectured, for the first time ever, in our paper *The chthonian legend*.

Earthquakes are a ghastly phenomenon and as such they have nothing to do with all that was unfoundedly supposed by Joyce Lussu and Anna Maria Piscitelli.

That was the 'original sin' of Project Elissa. A project deserving the greatest praise for its capability to attract public attention and private funding, to conduct actual prospect activities of the top of Mount Sibyl, to coordinate the efforts of many different scholars and academics, to contribute to a deeper knowledge of the sibilline phenomenon through a series of most interesting articles and books. A project that is to be considered as the last determined, organized effort carried out by passionate people on the sibilline subject (before the publication of the present series of articles *The Apennine Sibyl - A mystery and a legend*, which started in 2017).

But Project Elissa, while going after matriarchies and olistic knowledges and empowered women, just didn't think of earthquakes. They just missed the chance to start walking a path that — though far less gentle than wise women at villages — is currently unveiling the real, terrific origin of the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

That is why, in this framework, Project Elissa was doomed to failure.

And it could be no different outcome, if we read what a proficient, experienced writer like Maria Luciana Buseghin (the author of a fundamental work: *The last Sibyl*, 2012) had the occasion to annotate in her comprehensive, well-informed book on the Apennine Sibyl, after having reported many quotes from Joyce Lussu's books on this same subject (many of them also reported by Piscitelli in her articles):

«I must easily admit that many of [Joyce Lussu's] statements and inferences [on the Apennine Sibyl] appear to me as quite foolish — with all due respect for Lussu and her fully-committed life...».

Nonetheless, foolish as it might have been some traits of Project Elissa, it had the capability to uncover what nobody else had never been able to find out before: manuscript no. 40 at the historical archive of the municipality of Montemonaco.

So, while fully acknowledging the crucial, essential role of Project Elissa and Anna Maria Piscitelli in this astounding trove (she herself recalls, in her book on Antoine de la Sale, that the precious manuscript was ultimately «fished out under the drive of a sort of 'Sibilline Instinct'»), let's proceed with an analysis of the manuscripted parchment: a most interesting piece of evidence concerning the Apennine Sibyl and the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range in the fifteenth century.

We will mostly rely on the edition published by Project Elissa (*Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.*, 1998), which contains a full transcription and translation of the manuscript provided by an illustrious philologist and paleographer, Monsignor Giuseppe Ghilarducci.

4. Manuscript no. 40 preserved at the historical archive of Montemonaco

4.1 A spiritual trial and an acquittal at the foot of Mount Sibyl

«In the name of God. Amen. This is the acquittal and sentence of discharge that was rendered and pronounced in writing and enacted by the venerable and distinguished Christophorus de Guardarijs of Rieti, doctor of canon law, judge with jurisdiction over spiritual cases of the province of the March of Ancona by the authority of our most holy father in Christ and our lord, out of the divine providence, Pope N. V, and by the authority of the Holy Roman Church and the reverend father in Christ father and lord B. Archbishop of Ravenna, the most eminent governor of the said province of the March».

Fig. 25 - Manuscript no. 40 preserved at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco (single folium, recto), from Progetto Elissa, *Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.* (Montemonaco, 1998), p. 13

[In the original Latin text: «In Dei nomine. Amen. Hac est quadam sententia absolutoria et sententia assolutionis lata et data et in his scriptis sententialiter pronuntiata et promulgata fuit per venerabilem et eximum decretorum doctorem dominum Christophorum de Guardarijs de Reate iudicem in spiritualibus provintie Marchie Anconitane pro sanctissimo in Christo patre et domino domino nostro N. divina providentia pape V et pro sancta romana ecclesia et pro reverendo in Christo patre domino domino B. Archiepiscopo Ravenne et in prelibata provintia Marchie dignissimo governatore»].

This is the opening of manuscript no. 40, as it appears on its front side: a sentence is being rendered, and the defendants are found not guilty. The date, which we find towards the end of the manuscripted text, is «anno domini millesimo quadringentesimo quinquagesimo secundo indictione XV et die XV mensis junii», that is 1452, June 15th (the 'indictio' is a period of 15 years used in Roman and Middle Age time calculations — according to tabular values, year 1452 falls exactly within indiction no. 15, as correctly stated in the manuscript).

But who are the defendants? It is judge de Guardarijs himself who tells us the names of the parties against which the action had been brought:

«We, Christophorus, judge with jurisdiction over spiritual cases, for the law court sitting at our customary bench located and set in the said court [we rendered] the following acquittal and sentence of discharge in favor of the Priors, population, municipality and all the men in the land of Montemonaco as to the wickednesses, guilts, wrongdoings and crimes they allegedly committed, together with the perpetrated offences, the way we described, and as clearly reported here».

[In the original Latin text: «Nos Christophorus iudex in spiritualibus predittus, pro tribunali sedentes ad nostrum et dicte curie solitum banchum juris infra positum et confinatum, infrascriptam sententiam absolutoriam et sententia assolutionis in favorem predictorum priorum universitatem communis et homine terra Montis Monaci pro eorum malleficiis, culpis, excessibus et delictis ut dicebatur commissis et perpetratis dannis et in his scriptis et in hunc modum videlicet»].

Incredibly enough, the defendants are the very Priors of Montemonaco: the government of the commune. Together with the whole population («homines» in Latin) and the municipality itself.

We note that the wording used in the sentence is similar to that used in the ancient Charters of the municipality of Montemonaco: *Volumen Jurium Municipalium Hominum terrae Montis Monaci*, as we read in the edition printed in 1628, a reprint of a preceding edition dating to 1548 and containing more ancient provisions. At that time, Priors were in charge for the administration of the municipality of Montemonaco, in accordance with the decisions taken by a General Counsel formed by citizens residing in the various districts of the settlement.

* MONTE MONACO.

*I. — *Volumen Jurium Municipalium Hominum terrae Montis Monaci*, cui accesserunt infrascripta videlicet Rubrica celebrandae in posterum festivitatis Divi Benedicti Abbatis, Tassa Sportularum et Mercedis Domini Potestatis, Notarii, Actuarii et aliorum officialium, etc. — Impressum Amandulae, et iterum Maceratae. 1628. Apud Petrum Salvionum. *In folio*. Ra.

Questo titolo è nel dritto della 1.^a carta, nel cui verso v'è l'approvazione per la stampa, un piccolo proemio e una lettera di Giovanni Filippo Terponi Sentina. Nel dritto della 2.^a comincia la tavola, che termina al verso della 4.^a Nel dritto della seguente A hanno principio gli Statuti, che divisi in cinque libri terminano al verso della carta 44 con queste parole:

Impressum hoc praesens volumen Statutorum in Terra Amandulae per Magistrum Lucam Binum Mantuanum Paulo Tertio Sedente ut domino placuit Pontifice maximo, Procurante Provinciam Picenam pro Sacro Sanctae Romanae Illustris. et Reverendis. Domino Ranuccio Farnesio Cardinale S. Angeli de Latere Legato meritis. sub anno 1548. Et iterum Maceratae. Apud Petrum Salvionum Impressorem Cameralem. 1628.

Fig. 26 - The ancient Charters of the municipality of Montemonaco (from *Statuti, ordini e leggi dei municipii italiani*, part I, Bologna, 1876), p. 300

But what crimes, what criminal charges were all those people forced to face?

Before we proceed into the accusations, first we have to confront with a number of questions. Who is the judge? And who are the cryptic authorities indicated in the manuscript with single letters and numbers? What is this court «with jurisdiction over spiritual cases», and where is it located?

First of all, let's check all the listed issues. Then, we will deal with the sinister, blood-curdling crimes allegedly committed by the local rulers of Montemonaco and its inhabitants.

4.2 Administering justice in a province of the Papal States in the fifteenth century

At the mid of the fifteenth century, Montemonaco was a commune, a partially-independent local entity subject to the rule of the Pope in Rome, through the control of the March of Ancona, a papal province since the end of the twelfth century.

Fig. 27 - The March of Ancona, Mount Sibyl and Montemonaco in a later map (Abraham Ortelius' *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum*, Antwerp, 1603 - table following p. 86)

In 1452, the year in which our manuscript was written, the Pope was Nicholas V — «N V» as indicated in the text — and the papal governor of the March was the Archbishop of Ravenna, Bartolomeo Roverella — «B» in the manuscripted text.

Justice in the Marches, as well as in other papal provinces, was administered through the local General Curia, the law court controlled by the papal governor. At that time, there were four judges, each with jurisdiction on a specific domain (criminal, civil, appeal, and spiritual), as established by the *Constitutiones Aegidianae* issued by Cardinal Egidio Albornoz in 1357 (for a detailed insight on the subject see Pio Cartechini, *Due fondi giudiziari maceratesi: l'archivio della Curia generale della Marca e quello della Rota. Vicende e problemi*, in «*Pro tribunali sedentes*» - *Le magistrature giudiziarie dello Stato pontificio e i loro archivi*, conference proceedings edited by *Archivi per la Storia - Rivista dell'Associazione Nazionale Archivistica Italiana*, 1991, p. 81-94).

Christophorus de Guardarijs of Rieti at the time was the judge who had the «jurisdiction over spiritual cases» («in spiritualibus», in Latin), which included wrongdoings committed by clerics and other cases of ecclesiastic and religious relevance. His role is formally stated in the text by the customary Latin expression «pro tribunali sedentes» («sitting as a court»): an ancient, illustrious wording we find in sentences rendered by the Papal justice but already in use since Roman times, which we also find in the Gospels («Pilatus autem cum audisset hos sermones, adduxit foras Iesum: et sedit pro tribunali, in loco, qui dicitur Lithostrotos...»), John 19:13).

De Guardarijs writes that he was sitting at his «customary bench». But where was this bench placed? Further ahead in the manuscript, he also details his whereabouts as follows:

«... at his customary court bench on wickednesses' trials at the said curia, in accordance with customs, located by the palace of the chief magistrate of the land of Tolentino, where the judges of the curia render their sentences, with the bench placed by the said palace near the public square and neighboring streets».

[In the original Latin text: «... ad suum solitum banchum juris malleficiorum et ditte curie ut moris est situm suttus palatium potestatis

terre Tollentini ubi iudices curie redduntur jura quod bancum positum est
suttus dittum palacium iuxta plateam et vias publica undique»].

Fig. 28 - The excerpt which reads «Nos Christophorus iudex in spiritualibus...» from manuscript no. 40 preserved at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco (single folium, recto), as published in low resolution by Progetto Elissa, *Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.* (Montemonaco, 1998), p. 13

So the sentence was rendered by de Guardarijs in Tolentino, a small town of the March of Ancona. But why the General Curia was located in this tiny, secondary settlement?

Historically, for most of the time the General Curia of the March of Ancona has been located in another city of the province, Macerata, together with the office of the papal governor; nonetheless, for many reasons, the Curia's headquarters have been wandering, through the centuries, across different towns of the Marches. And, in 1452, the year of our manuscript, the Curia was exactly in Tolentino, as attested in the *Essay on the memories of the town of Tolentino* written in 1789 by a local scholar, Carlo Santini:

«The members of the public council [of Tolentino, editor's note] of that time sent a plea to the Governor of the March so as he moved his own residence and that of the General Curia to Tolentino [...] It was in that periodo of time that the Town of Macerata was selected as the headquarters of the General Curia and the Governor's residence; but shortly after, as our municipality set forth new pleas, even more appealing, it won the concession, as attested in the book of Reforms of the years 1451, 1452, 1453».

Fig. 29 - The transfer of the General Curia of the March of Ancona to Tolentino in 1451 (from Carlo Santini's *Saggio di memorie della città di Tolentino*, Macerata, 1789, p. 147-148)

[In the original Italian text: «i pubblici Consiglieri di quel tempo per mezzo di Ambasciatori giudicarono di supplicare il Legato della Marca, affinché fissasse la residenza sua, e della Curia generale in Tolentino [...] Allora fu, che in tal'occasione venne destinata la Città di Macerata per luogo della Curia generale, e per residenza del Legato; ma poco dopo avendo avanzate il nostro Comune nuove, e più premurose istanze, ottenne la grazia, come si ha dal libro di dette Riformanze degli anni 1451, 1452, 1453»].

The judges of the Curia were assisted at their bench by a number of notaries public for the performance of clerical and secretarial tasks, keeping the records and authenticating the court orders. And we retrieve specific references to this aspect in manuscript no. 40:

«... [this sentence] was written, read and published by myself, Sir Victorinum Ascentij of Sancta Victoria, by the imperial authority notary public and ordinary judge and now notary and official with reference to spiritual cases of the said province of the March [...] to all and each of the said things I was present and was required to write down, so I wrote them down and published them and put my customary sign on it all».

[In the original Latin text: «... et scripta, letta et publicata per me Victorinum ser Ascentij de Sancta Victoria publicum imperiali auctoritate

notarium et juducem ordinarium et nunc notarium et officialem in spritualibus provintie Marchie preditte [...] predittis omnibus et singulis prefui rogatusque scribere scripsi et publicavi signumque meum apposui consuetum»].

Sir Victorinum Ascentij was a notary public of Santa Vittoria in Matenano, a hamlet set between the Sibillini Mountain Range and the Adriatic Sea. He was of imperial appointment («imperiali auctoritate»), as the momentous powers of authentication bestowed upon notaries public were to be granted by the highest authorities (including the Pope, «sacri palatii notarius»), even though municipalities and bishops could also appoint their notaries.

Sir Victorinum doesn't omit to sign the document with his own 'signum tabellionis', a personal mark («signumque meum apposui consuetum») with a unique shape which attests to the genuineness of his hand and written elaboration: a sort of graphic seal that notaries public have been using throughout the centuries.

Fig. 30 - The 'signum tabellionis' written by notary public Victorinum Ascentij on manuscript no. 40 preserved at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco (single folium, recto), as published in low resolution by Progetto Elissa, *Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.* (Montemonaco, 1998), p. 13

And the defendants? They were represented in the spiritual case by their own attorney:

«Before the court it appeared sir Sanctes of sir Nutius of Santa Vittoria, lawyer and defender of the said community in front of the said judge sitting for the court with jurisdiction over spiritual cases as detailed before, and submitted a plea for the acquittal of the Priors, municipality and men of the land of Montemonaco, so as to set them free from whatever is stated in the proceedings carried out against them».

[In the original Latin text: «Ante omnia comparuit ser Sanctes ser Nutij de Santa Victoria syndicus et procurator dicte communitatis coram prefato domino spiritaliter sedente pro tribunali ut supra et petujt predictos priores commune et homines terre Montis Monaci predict absolvi et liberari a contentis inquisitione formata contra ipsos omni modo et cetera»].

So the whole trial is complete with all its fundamental players — to them we must only add «Marino Mattei, Petrus Paulo Dominici, cleric of the church of Tolentino, Johannes Colo Rainaldi and sir Benedetto Nicolai of Tolentino, and sir Ludovico of Johannes Blancus of Monte Lumpori», all of them «witnesses about the said matters, summoned and, after attendance, queried» («testibus ad predicta vocatis, habitis et rogatis»).

And now, the time has come to address the core issue of these judicial, 'spiritual' proceedings, the accusations confronted by the people of Montemonaco and their leaders, who at the time found themselves dangerously indicted before the mighty jurisdiction of the Church:

«Against the Priors, population, municipality and all the men in the land of Montemonaco, and any of their connections we proceeded with the means and strength of the inquisition out of our judicial office, will, authority, powers and role, on and around this whole matter...»

[In the original Latin text: «Priores, universitatem, comune et homines terre Montis Monaci contra quos et quolibet issorum processimus per modum et vigore inquisitionis ex nostroque curie offitio, arbitrio, auctoritate, potestate et balia in eo de eo et super eo...»].

But what were the charges? And why were they ranked as 'spiritual'?

We will see that in the whole matter, in this fifteenth-century trial we will find the magical, sinister hand of a figure we well know: the Sibyl and her eerie abode set up there, amid the high cliffs of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

4.3 Montemonaco under trial: the accusations

A court, a judge, a notary public. A multitude of defendants: the inhabitants of Montemonaco and their Priors. And charges. Accusations against them all.

But what crimes did they commit? What charges were all those people forced to face?

It was a matter of peculiar visitors, necromantic arts, and the Sibyl:

«... during the months of July, August and September of the current year, scienter, deliberately, knowingly and with purposeful and intentional resolution, they accommodated and housed in the commune and provided support, advice and help to each and all of them, i.e. sir Angelo from Aversa and Joshua from the Kingdom [of Naples] and his companions to exercise alchemy and with the will to consecrate some evil and fiendish books at the lake of the Sibyl, with the will and intention to follow the fiendish art, and continue with their art in scorn of the Divine Majesty and so endangering the Christian faith to the damage and disdain of the souls of many Christians».

[In the original Latin text: «... de anno presenti et mensibus julii, augusti et settembris ditti anni scienter, dolose, studiose et appensato animo et intentione retinuerunt et receptaverunt in comunis ac ipsis et cuilibet ipsorum prestiterunt ausilium, consilium et favorem videlicet dopno Angelus de Adversa et Josuè de partibus regnis et sui sotiis in fatiendo archimiam et volendo sacrare libros nonnullos malignos et diabolicos ad lacum Sibille animo et intentione sequendi artem diabolicam et in eorum arte continuandi ignominiam divine Maiestatis et in preiuditium fidei christiane et dapnum et vilipendium nonnullarum animarum fidelium»].

So, during the summer, visitors coming from abroad (the Kingdom of Naples) had established their headquarters in the small hamlet of Montemonaco, and went up and down to and from Mount Vettore and the Lake of Pilate (also known as 'the Lake of the Sibyl', as already attested by Antoine de la Sale) to consecrate their spellbooks to the demons.

Fig. 31 - The Lake of Pilate, or of the Sibyl

And those foreigners weren't alone. In that same period other necromancers walked the paths which led from Montemonaco to the neighbouring mountains:

«In addition to that, certain people coming from the Kingdom of Naples and Spain were housed and accommodated in a house belonging to Mr. Catarino of the said land, located in the same place, because they intended to consecrate fiendish books and perform magical arts, that is they exercised alchemy in the said house».

[In the original Latin text: «Item dum certi de partibus regni Neapolitani et Spanie stabant et residebant in quadam domum ser Catarini de dicta terra, situata in dicta terra, causa quod intendebant sacrare nonnullos libros

diabolicos et artem magicam exercere ut est archimiam in dicta domo faciebant»].

Thus Spaniards were also there for the very same purposes. Lots of people were in Montemonaco in 1452, during the summer, to pay their visits to the Lake of the Sibyl and, possibly, to the Cave too.

So the manuscript just fully confirms what we know it used to happen in Montemonaco at the mid the fifteenth century, as we already know from multiple sources, including Antoine de la Sale, Enea Silvio Piccolomini, Felix Hemmerlin, Flavio Biondo, St. James of the Marches and Bernardino Bonavoglia of Foligno — all illustrated in the previous paragraphs of the present article.

Fig. 32 - The words «julii, augusti et settembris» appearing in manuscript no. 40 preserved at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco (single folium, recto), as published in low resolution by Progetto Elissa, *Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.* (Montemonaco, 1998), p. 13

We incidentally note that an inconsistency on dates appears to be present: the parchment sheet is dated 1452, June 15th, but the events which are described in the text would have occurred «during the months of July, August and September of the current year», i.e. after the manuscript itself was written. Of course this specific point makes up an issue and will need further investigation; however, for a deeper analysis a high-resolution copy of the text will be needed.

Now let's go back to the occurrences mentioned in the manuscript. What was exactly going on, there in Montemonaco? Let's investigate further this fascinating case.

4.4 Montemonaco under trial: the manifest 'mens rea'

After reading the accusations, a question immediately arises: were the inhabitants and the Priors of Montemonaco to be found necessarily liable for the charges as listed above?

Shouldn't they be considered, maybe, as mere passive subjects, unwillingly overwhelmed by all the hustle and bustle that unwanted foreigners used to bring in and around their small, peaceful village, sitting placidly on a hill raising just in front of Mount Sibyl?

Didn't they lack a 'mens rea' condition, i.e. the actual will and intention to purposely support those foreign visitors in carrying out their forbidden activities up there, and committing spiritual crimes so as to «endanger the Christian faith»?

Fig. 33 - The sentences «libros nonnullos malignos et diabolicos ad lacum Sibille» and «in absotiano predictos ad dittum lacum Sibille» appearing in manuscript no. 40 preserved at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco (single folium, recto), as published in low resolution by Progetto Elissa, *Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.* (Montemonaco, 1998), p. 13

But judge de Guardarijs is unequivocal: he writes of a deliberate «support, advice and help» provided to the foreigners by the villagers. And he also adds the following:

«And not limiting to that but even adding more evil to the evil, the said Priors, population, municipality and all the men, helped and supported sir Angelo and his companions as to their sustenance and provision, so as they could more effectively fulfill their wicked wishes, bread and wine and any other needed supply, and also accompanied them up to the said lake of the Sibyl, in spite of the Christian faith».

[In the original Latin text: «Et non contenti predictis sed mala mali addendo prestiterunt preditti priores commune et homines et universitas prenominatis, dopno Angelo et suis sotijs auxilium et favorem in dapno predittis per eorum sostentationem et vittum ut habilis eorum pessimum appetitum executioni mandarent, panem, vinum et alia necessaria pro victu et cuiusque ipsorum et in absotiano predictos ad dittum lacum Sibille de causa contra fidem cristianam»].

So the citizens of Montemonaco, instead of driving them off, seem to have welcomed all such truly-peculiar visitors, without omitting to serve them in their accommodation and lodging needs, and also acting as guides for people who certainly were not experienced with the specific terrain.

They weren't just passive. They actively helped the foreigners in carrying out their prohibited practices.

In this framework, the price to be paid by the inhabitants of Montemonaco and their priors for the assistance provided to such foreigners, involved in necromantic activities at the Lake of Pilate, could have been the stake or the gallows.

It may be profitable to recall the excerpts drawn from the sermon *De sortilegiis* written by St. James of Marches which narrate of that woman with «the figure of an enchantress, similar to a fiend» («faciem incantatricis, quasi diabolicam») who was «burnt in Perugia» («combusta Perusii»); or that other one, the «old woman of Rome, known as Funicella» («vetula Rome, nominata Funicella»), who underwent a trial carried out by an «inquisitor» of St. James' same Franciscan order, and was burnt as well («et combusta est»); and a further woman, Santecia, also burnt in Perugia; and the two elderly women, who in the excruciating pain of the stake desperately cried out for the name of the Devil («et combuste sunt clamantes dyabolum»).

Et si non credis respice ad faciem incantatricis, quasi diabolicam, quia semper in ipsa habitat diabolus, sicut hic, superius, dictum est et ut confessa fuit Scuncia, combusta Perusii.

Item, quedam vetula Rome, nominata^b Funicella, interfecit 65 pueros et coxit brachium filii sui mortui pro incantationibus. Et dicebat sibi^c diabolus sic^d, quod non erat peccatum interficere^e innocentes, quia salvabantur^f. Et hoc dixit mihi magister Nicolaus de Roma, ordinis nostri, tum^g inquisitor, et combusta est.

Item^h, quedam diabolica vetula de Gualdo de Nuceria, combusta in Perusia, nomine Santeccia, que fecit innumerabilia mala, inter que confessa est quod occidit pueros 50 et etiam sucavit sanguinem

Item idem frater^s Matheus^t invenit duas vetulas super altare extra portam civitatis, abeuntes insimul pro confusione Christi. Postea in trivio nude loquebantur cum dyabolo, interfectis multis pueris; combuste sunt clamantes dyabolum.

Fig. 34 - Enchantresses sent to the stake from *De sortilegiis*, a sermon includes in Iacobus de Marchia's fifteenth-century *Sermones Dominicales*, edited by Renato Lioi (Falconara, 1978), p. 424 and 425

But we may also recall what Antoine de la Sale himself said in his *The paradise of Queen Sibyl* as to the capital punishments incurred by those who came to the sinister shores of the Lake of Pilate with evil intentions:

«For this reason when the local people, who take great care in that, find someone there, he his not welcome. And not much time has elapsed since two men were caught, one of them being a priest. The priest was brought to the said town of Norcia and there was martyred and burnt. The other was slaughtered into pieces and then thrown into the lake from the very people who had caught them both».

[In the original French text: «Et porce quant les gens du pays qui ad ce prennent moult grant garde y trouvent aucun il est mal venu. Et navoit pas long temps quel y fut prins deux hommes dont lun estoit prestre ce preste fut admene a la dicte cite de norce et la fut martire et ars. Lautre fut taille a pieces et puis boute dedens le lac par ceulz qui les avoient prins»].

les fous & bnis de la contree ¶ Et volente nū
les gens du pais qui ad ce prennent nū gūit

gūide y treuuent aucun Il est mal venu Et
nauoit pas long temps quil y fut pris deux
hommes dont lun estoit prestre ce prestre fut
admené a la dite cite de norce & la fut martue
& auē ¶ Lautre fut taillē a piēces & puis loute
dedens le lac par ceulz qui les auoient pris

Fig. 35 - The killing of supposed necromancers at the Lake of Pilate in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 4v - 5r)

And Arnold von Harff, a German knight who in the years 1496-1499 carried out a journey across many countries, and visited the Cave and Lake accompanied by an official from Norcia or Castelluccio, specified that

«... after midday he rode with us up the mountain to where there was a little lake. By this lake was a little chapel like a holy house, in which was a small altar. [...] Certain persons frequented this altar and vowed themselves to evil spirits, performing their necromancy there. [...] When the people could suffer this no longer they made complaint to the castellan of this castle, who thereupon set up gallows between the holy house and the lake, and forbade that anyone should thenceforth exercise necromancy at the altar, and that any who did so should be hanged on the gallows».

[In the original German text: «Item wir tzogen myt dem casteleyne den berch vss, doe loyt hee vnss zo gast off dat sloessgen, dae hee vns den myttaich gar gude tzier an dede. Item nae myttaghe reyt he mit vns oeuen off desen berch. Daer off stund eyn kleyne staynde see. By deser see stunt eyn kleyn cappelgen wie eyn heyligen huys. Dae inne stunt eyn kleyn altair. Dae van saicht he vns, dat vurtzijden doe die kunst der nigermancien in der werlt vmb gynck, doe lieffen dese seluigen off desen altair ind beswoeren dae den boesen geyst, drijuende dae yere nigremancie. Item as

dat dan geschiet was hoyff sich off dat wasser des cleynen sees in eynen wolcken ind quam dan weder her aeff mit eyne donresslage, verdrenckende dat gantze lant dae vmbtrijnt drij off vier mylen, so dat dat jair geyn korn dae en woys. Item dit en wolde dat volck nyet me lijden ind claget dem castelangen dys sloss, der van stund an eyn vpgereckde galge leyss settzen tusschen dat heyligen huysgen in die see ind dede verbieden dat niemans me off dem elter nigermancie doyn en suyldt. Der aber dat dede den seuldt man an die galge hangen»].

stunden noch offen. Item wir tzogen myt dem casteleyne
 15 den berch vss, doe loyt hee vnss zo gast off dat sloessgen,
 dae hee vns den myttaich gar gude tzier an dede. Item
 nae myttaghe reyrt he mit vns oeuem off desen berch. daer
 off stund eyn kleyne staynde see. by deser see stunt eyn
 kleyn cappelgen wie eyn heyligen huys. dae inne stunt eyn
 20 kleyn altair. dae van saicht he vns, dat vurtzijden doe die
 kunst der nigermancien in der werlt vmb gynck, doe lieffen
 dese seluigen off desen altair ind beswoeren dae den boesen
 geyst, drijuende dae yere nigremancie. Item as dat dan
 geschiet was hoyff sich off dat wasser des cleynen sees in
 25 eynen wolcken ind quam dan weder her aeff mit eyne
 donresslage, verdrenckende dat gantze lant dae vmbtrijnt
 drij off vier mylen, so dat dat jair geyn korn dae en woys.
 Item dit en wolde dat volck nyet me lijden ind claget
 dem castelangen dys sloss, der van stund an eyn vpgereckde
 30 galge leyss settzen tusschen dat heyligen huysgen in die
 see ind dede verbieden dat niemans me off dem elter niger-
 mancie doyn en suyldt. der aber dat dede den seuldt man
 an die galge hangen. Item dit vertzalt vnss der casteleyne

Fig. 36 - The excerpt on the gallows at the Lake of Pilate from a printed edition of *Die Pilgerfahrt des Ritters Arnold von Harff* edited by E. Von Groote (Cologne, 1860), p. 38

So the whole matter was utterly delicate, and could not be managed carelessly or recklessly, because death by spiritual justice, as enforced by the Church's courts, was just at hand.

The same Enea Silvia Piccolomini, when writing about the notorious fame of the Sibillini Mountain Range in his letter *De Monte Veneris*, appears to maintain a restrained attitude and a fully circumspect approach, as he holds that «I have never witnessed facts of that sort, nor have I ever cared to; since what is apprehended only through sin, it is much safer not to know at all» (in the original Latin text: «haec non vidi, nec vidisse curavi. Nam quod peccato discitur melius est ignorasse»).

A century later, it will be Leandro Alberti, a Dominican friar, who will write, in his *General description of Italy*, ominous words which express all the severity of the authorities against the fiendish art being performed on those Apennine cliffs:

«On the portion of this towering mountain facing eastward, it can be seen that most famous Lake of which tales are told about the conjuring of devils summoned by sorcerers, who would speak to them. If such accounts were true, it would certainly deserve severe condemnation, and such witchcrafts should be hardly punished under both Canonical and Imperial laws».

[In the original Italian text: «Vedesi alla parte de quest'altissimo monte, (che riguarda all'oriente) quel tanto famoso Lago de'l quale se dice che vi apparenno i demoni costretti dagli incantatori, & che qui vi parlano con essi. Che se così fusse sarebbe cosa molto biasimevole, & tali incantamenti meriterebbero gravissime punitioni secondo le leggi Canoniche & Imperiali»].

Fig. 37 - Visits to the Lake of Pilate and punishments as mentioned in Leandro Alberti's *Descrittione di tutta l'Italia* (Bologna, 1550), p. 248

Despite all that, the inhabitants of Montemonaco appeared to be very glad and proactive in serving the many foreigners who pushed themselves as far as their small hamlet to reach the magical, elevated sites connected to the Apennine Sibyl, the demons, and the exercise of the prohibited arts of alchemy and necromancy.

Isn't this 'mens rea' of the most self-evident sort? Weren't the locals in Montemonaco fully guilty of all the nefarious charges ascribed to them?

Shouldn't they have deserved the harshest, the severest of the punishments, both individually and collectively?

Possibly not. Because they were all acquitted.

And we are going to see how it could have happened in the next paragraphs.

4.5 An acquittal for everybody

«We, Christophorus de Guardarijs, [...] judge with jurisdiction over spiritual cases, the said Priors, population, municipality and all the men in the land of Montemonaco we declare not guilty and release, and we intend to consider them as acquitted and released from the said proceedings; and from the charges referred in the trial and stated in it we declare them not guilty and fully release them as much as we can, and each and all of them we equally render acquitted».

[In the original Latin text: «Nos Christophorus de Guardarijs, [...] iudex in spiritualibus [...] predittos priores universitatem commune et homines terre Montis Monaci absolvimus et liberamus et pro absolutis et liberatis haberi volumus a supraditta inquisitione et contentis in causa et in his scriptis absolvimus et liberamus omni modo meliori quo possimus ipsos et quelibet ipsorum reddimus similliter absolutos»].

Everybody was acquitted. All the charges against the defendants were dropped. Montemonaco was found not guilty.

As we said before, the punishment that the inhabitants of Montemonaco and their Priors deserved for the support granted to necromancers and alchemists, involved in prohibited, possibly fiendish activities at the Lake of the Sibyl, could have been the stake or the gallows, or the excommunication to say the least.

Instead, there were no punishments, no stakes, no gallows. Even though, clearly enough, the Priors and the local residents had been providing a comprehensive support to foreign alchemists and necromancers.

But how can it all be?

The key to this most favorable sentence is in the following: they were all acquitted, luckily enough, because the judge was not in the capacity of retrieving any sound evidence of their guilt: «we could not ascertain the actual truth of the facts» («non potuimus [...] perfectam rei veritatem invenire»).

Fig. 38 - The sentence «... non potuimus examinare et perfectam rei veritatem invenire idcirco» appearing in manuscript no. 40 preserved at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco (single folium, recto), as published in low resolution by Progetto Elissa, *Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.* (Montemonaco, 1998), p. 13

De Guardarijs was unable to assess how the events actually went. There was, in Montemonaco, an astounding lack of local witnesses. And where were the alchemists? They had just gone. Vanished. Disappeared.

So there was an issue of missing evidence. Who could really tell what had truly happened in Montemonaco in that summer of year 1452? The whole matter seemed to shrink to rumors and hearsays only.

And judge Christophorus de Guardarijs could not but issue his sentence of acquittal. The case was basically dismissed.

But what had actually happened in Montemonaco, that summer, at the mid of the fifteenth century?

Something really interesting was going on at the small hamlet which faces the crowned summit of Mount Sibyl. And we are going to find out in the next chapter, by navigating the hidden meanders of the sentence.

Meanders which contain lots of intriguing — and even amusing — information.

Fig. 39 - A vision of today's Montemonaco, still retaining its medieval ambiance

5. *What was going on in Montemonaco in 1452?*

5.1 *Events, facts and circumstances according to Project Elissa*

«In the fourteenth and fifteenth century, and perhaps even earlier than that, in the lands around the Sibillini Mountain Range primeval cults devoted to feminine archetypes powerfully resurfaced again, with shamanic features. Such cults, influenced by the celtic sagas, inspired in their mystical and epical forms the chivalric literature and courtly love themes set in central Italy; while, in a more sensual, erotic form those same cults contributed to heretical sects and orgiastic sabbaths later attributed to witches».

This is what Anna Maria Piscitelli wrote in her book *Antoine de la Sale - Viaggio nei misteri della Sibilla* (p. 31) in 1999 when mentioning manuscript no. 40, already discovered two years before and published the preceding year: this remote region of the Apennines was a territory in which very strong was «the ancient sensual cult of Nature [...] centered on the magnification of the ritual energies of life and fertility of the earth and of all living creatures», made up by «shamanic practices»; such most

ancient «naturalistic tradition, since time immemorial» handed over across generations, underwent a combination with the more recent, late-medieval «alchemic» tradition, was also accommodated by the local populations: because «the people of the Sibillini Mountain Range», added Piscitelli, «attended to alchemic rituals which were considered as heretical...» (p. 32-35).

So according to the vision proposed by the founder and inspirer of Project Elissa, the inhabitants of the Sibillini Mountains, and chiefly the people of Montemonaco (with their special relationship with the sibilline cliff), were to be considered as the keepers of an antique tradition, lost in the mists of millennia and rooted in the feminine archetype that was the Project's basic assumption: a tradition that combined forgotten crafts on energy, life and healing methods with the alchemic knowledge that had been resurrected in Europe in the course the Middle Ages.

In this model, sure enough the residents of Montemonaco were fully involved in magical, alchemic and even 'shamanic' practices on their own. Here is what Piscitelli adds on the topic:

«Alchemy was classified amid the heresies that were sanctioned by the Holy Inquisition and in 1452 all the land of Montemonaco, in which this Art was freely performed together with a natural 'shamanism' of Italic origin, was on the brink of paying the consequences of all this by being excommunicated, as attested in the manuscripted parchment retrieved in its Municipal Archive» (p. 34).

According to Piscitelli, the inhabitants of Montemonaco perfectly knew about magic and alchemy, and used to play with both forbidden arts; in addition, they willingly supported foreign visitors in the performance of their own rituals on the cliffs of Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl:

«Not only the people of the Sibillini Mountain Range practiced the arts of alchemy, considered as heretical; but also knights came from everywhere and — behind the screen of an elusive consultation of the Sibilline Oracle — they actually sought to learn the secrets of the Art...» (p. 35).

Fig. 40 - A few of the many ancient architectural elements — these were retrieved in Cornaloni, an ancient abandoned settlement in the territory of Montegallo — which Progetto Elissa considered as a token of a widespread presence of hermeticism and alchemy in the eastern versant of the Sibillini Mountain Range in past centuries (from *Le terre della Sibilla Appenninica - Antico crocevia di idee scienze e cultura*, Montemonaco, 1999), p. 82 and 100

In Project Elissa's conjecture, we find local people in fifteenth-century Montemonaco fully conversant in a number of forbidden disciplines, led by Priors who certainly are not unfamiliar with the same sort of knowledge.

Virtually, in Piscitelli's vision the small hamlet of the Sibillini Mountain Range was almost a nest of heretics, though completely inoffensive and marked by a profound erudition, as further detailed in the book *Errante erotica eretica - L'icona Sibillina fra Cecco d'Ascoli e Osvaldo Licini* (p. 105):

«Already from the fifteenth century, between the sixteenth and the seventeenth, and up to the eighteenth century, particularly in the territories lying around Mount Sibyl, alchemy was freely exercised mainly among the ranks of the learned aristocrats in the municipalities and hamlets of the inland, as the heirs of even remoter adepts of the sciences of nature: those distant italic-picene, shamanic ancestors who possessed that sort of knowledge».

To the Author of the present paper, this picture appears to be far too extreme. Too dramatic. Too serious. And even a bit naive.

Certainly the Sibillini Mountain Range is a land marked by some peculiarities, owing to the presence of specific legendary material which arises — in the view of your Author — from earthquakes and their mighty, terrific, recurrent manifestation in the area, or — according to Piscitelli and Project Elissa — to some sort of ancestral feminine archetype connected to positive concepts such as life, peace and healing, and later to natural magic and alchemy.

Nonetheless, we don't think at all that the inhabitants of Montemonaco were so interested, nor skilled, in past centuries, in magical arts and practices; the same way as we do not believe that they were so impressed by their own legendary tradition concerning a Sibyl and a demonic lake.

Basically, just like today, the people of Montemonaco were sound, sturdy inhabitants of a mountainous region: they worked in their fields, they went for timber in woods, they were hunters, they had locally their social and religious life. Specifically, they knew their mountains well, and they also perfectly knew that fairy tales are just mere fairy tales. Life, real life, hard life was something different.

For sure, there were people in Montemonaco who were fascinated by the old tales, or who entertained themselves in performing magical or alchemical arts, both in the populace and the higher classes (Piscitelli herself retrieved a number of old alchemic manuscripts, dating back to the sixteenth-seventeenth century, forgotten in the basement of the ancient home in Montemonaco to which she had moved). But they were a marginal fraction of the local society, as it always happens in all human

communities, being men and women mainly engaged in earning a living, with no time available for addressing quirky legends or cranky sciences. This is true today, and was truer in the Middle Ages, when life was much harder.

Fig. 41 - The mountains towards Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl as seen from Montemonaco

All we said does not mean that Montemonaco was not renowned in Europe as a place suitable for carrying out magical or alchemical rituals, due to the outstanding presence of an eerie Sibyl's Cave and a sinister Lake of Pilate: a peculiar aspect that was perfectly known to foreigner as well as to locals.

And here is where it comes, for the inhabitants of Montemonaco, the chance to earn a living. As we will illustrate in the next paragraph, drawing some illuminating hints from our manuscript no. 40.

5.2 Events, facts and circumstances according to a sounder, more reasonable interpretation

So what was actually happening in Montemonaco, that summer, at the mid of the fifteenth century?

Most probably, it was just happening what used to happen there every summer, with the good weather: people coming from abroad flocked to Montemonaco to visit the famous legendary sites of the Lake and Cave, lying up on the crests of Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl, in search of a place where to perform magical arts or in an attempt to penetrate the hidden, lascivious realm of the Apennine Sibyl.

Fig. 42 - Mount Sibyl in summer

As we already detailed at the beginning of the present article, we must stress again the point that the two locations, in the fifteenth century, were already significantly renowned, following the mentions provided by Petrus Berchorius, Fazio degli Uberti, Andrea da Barberino, Antoine de la Sale, Felix Hemmerlin, and others.

With their literary works, all of them had just imparted new momentum to a rumour which was already widely spread across Italy and abroad. At that time, in 1452, everybody in Europe knew about the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate.

So people did use to come to Montemonaco. Obviously they came during the summer season, when there was no snow, and an easy climb to the magical peaks was more comfortably achievable.

They came, that year at the middle of the fifteenth century. And, for sure, this was not the first time they came. It was just just another summer in a row: not always the same people, as travellers speaking different languages continued to flock each year to Montemonaco, during the good seasons, to meet the famous legends.

When perusing the manuscript, it clearly appears that the inhabitants of Montemonaco were well aware of this remarkable flow of tourists of so peculiar a sort. They weren't surprised nor disappointed at all.

And, most of all, they seemed to basically appreciate all the fuss brought in town by the foreigners, who were there to carry out forbidden rituals on the neighboring mountains. So much they liked it that they did not even consider to report that spiritually-illegal hustle to the papal justice, i.e. to the General Curia and its judge «with jurisdiction over spiritual cases».

Fig. 43 - «Priores, universitatem, comune et homines terre Montis Monaci...», from manuscript no. 40 preserved at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco (single folium, recto), as published in low resolution by Progetto Elissa, *Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.* (Montemonaco, 1998), p. 13

In fact, what do we read in the acquittal? We read the following words:

«... According to public rumours and following what was referred to us as an amazing voice, not arising from ill-intentioned or deceitful people but, on the contrary, by honest and trustworthy persons, and not in a single occasion but more than once, it came to our ears and to this spiritual jurisdiction and institution the information that the formers [the Priors and inhabitants of Montemonaco, editor's note], having removed from their sight the vision of God and keeping before their eyes the fiendish enemy of human kind, during the months of July, August and September of the current year...».

[In the original Latin text: «... Fama publica precedente et clamosa insinuatione referente non quidem a malivolis et suspectis sed potius a veridicis et fide dignis hominibus et personis non semel tantum sed sepe sepius ad aures et notitiam supra ditti dominij spiritualis et sue curie audita relatae pervenit quod prenominati, Deum pre oculis non habendo sed potius inimicum human generis, de anno presenti et mensibus julii, august et settembris...»].

So the papal judge in Tolentino happened to know about the presence of such ill-intentioned foreigners in Montemonaco not from the local authorities (who should have reported that to the higher administrative and judicial levels of the Papal States) but only out of rumours and hearsays, which eventually triggered the activation of the jurisdictional procedure.

This means that the people and local authorities in Montemonaco certainly did not use to report anything to their bosses as to their odd summer visitors coming from abroad.

But why?

Did it happen because the inhabitants of Montemonaco were all alchemists and magicians, just like those visitors coming from foreign countries?

As we noted earlier, this is a naive interpretation of the facts described in the manuscript.

The true reason is much simpler and down to earth.

The Priors and residents of Montemonaco did not use to report their odd, weird visitors because — we can easily imagine — for them it was a lucrative business. An utterly rewarding summer business.

Let's try to figure out in our minds the situation that was taking place in Montemonaco around 1450: wealthy people coming from abroad — actually simpletons fascinated by the fairy tales concerning a magical Sibyl and a demonic Lake — flocked to this small, secluded hamlet, their pockets and bags full of foreign pieces of gold, ready to stay there for a whole summer to carry out their silly attempts and pointless rituals up there on the elevated peaks raising just a few miles away: why should they have repelled them? Why not take full advantage, instead, of all those rich, aristocratic tourists, many accompanied by their retinue, all most willing to cut profitable (for the locals) deals concerning the accommodation in private houses, the daily trips to Mount Sibyl and Mount Vettore, the supply of tools and horses, the provision of food, and gallons after gallons of wine?

«... [They] helped and supported them as to their sustenance and provision, [...] bread and wine and any other needed supply, and also accompanied them up to the said lake of the Sibyl...» («sostentationem et vittum... panem, vinum et alia necessaria», in Latin).

Fig. 44 - An artistic vision of a medieval meal served to distinguished visitors

That was a true bounty for the inhabitants of Montemonaco. And it happened and happened again every year, each blessed summer: a veritable gift from a benevolent God, who sent to them so many nice, gullible people. In large quantities. Wealthy and ready to spend their money in the village, for food, drinking, accommodation, and foolish trips to the nearby mountains.

A lot of money. For lots of (surely overcharged) services. Until the visitors' well-stocked pockets were cleaned out of cash, before they departed from town.

Fig. 45 - A heap of ancient coins with a golden florin on top

In this scenario, Montemonaco in the fifteenth century was no nest of alchemists. The locals just happened to exploit, in business terms, the peculiar attractiveness featured by their renowned legends.

The market was demanding all that. A market mainly made up by foreign well-to-do visitors coming in summers. And the residents were happy to meet market demands and cut profitable deals with foreigners, in exchange for fresh, tinkling money, be this in the form of nice silver groschen or shiny golden florins.

But how can we prove or confirm our business-oriented conjecture?

Let's read further from manuscript no. 40. We will find additional hints to the fact that we are not far from truth.

5.3 Shunning (capital) punishment by a hair

So, according to our assumption, in the fifteenth century, in Montemonaco, on the eastern side of the Sibillini Mountain Range, the surveillance held by local authorities against self-styled sorcerers and would-be alchemists flocking from abroad to the eerie Lake and Cave high above was, to say the least, a bit scarce and markedly ineffective.

In fact, we assume that the whole village liked a lot better to give foreign visitors a helping hand — fools as they turned out to be, all engaged as they were in performing their silly, preposterous, forbidden activities at the Cave's entrance, or playing their magical, prohibited tricks by the Lake's shores.

But all those fools were willing to pay silver and even golden coins to the villagers, in exchange for lodging, boarding and guided tour services.

Nonetheless, as we illustrated in the previous paragraphs, the policy pursued by the central and provincial papal authorities was to prosecute those visitors, in an attempt to limit the access to the two famous legendary sites. And actually manuscript no. 40 reports that, as soon as those authorities came to know of all the hustle and bustle that was going on in Montemonaco that summer, they immediately hurried to the spot and applied the due penalties and countermeasures to stop it all:

«... sir Angelo, who was named in this trial, was caught and imprisoned by us and our office and handed over to the local authority in Montemonaco and immediately held and detained...».

[In the original Latin text: «... predittus dominus Angelus in preditta inquisitione nominatus, fuit captus et captivatus per nos et nostrum officium et in manibus potentatis terre Montis Monaci tunc et nunc positus ed detemptus...»].

Thus poor sir Angelo, the wretched alchemist from the Kingdom of Naples, was taken and detained in Montemonaco by order of the General Curia and judge de Guardarijs, «with jurisdiction over spiritual cases», for subsequent prosecution: and — if we remember the words that St. James of Marches

used to utter in his sermons in similar cases — his tragic destiny would certainly have been 'combustion' on the stake.

Fig. 46 - Templars being burnt at the stake (manuscript BL Royal 20 C VII preserved at the British Library, London, fourteenth century), folium 44v

But, incredibly enough, sir Angelo succeeded in averting the excruciating flames. How could this be?

The mistake was to have «handed [him] over to the local authority in Montemonaco», instead of transferring him to the General Curia in Tolentino. In Montemonaco, sir Angelo had friends.

In fact, there at the village lying by the slopes of Mount Sibyl, for a strange string of occurrences, he just fled, presumably heading right home to Aversa:

«... and that afterwards the said Angelo, out of carelessness and guilt of that same local authority has broken free from their very hands and eluded their control and hastily ran away, as was reported to us by the said authority and many persons from this land...».

[In the original Latin text: «...et denu ipse dominus Angelus ex defectu et culpa ipsius potentatis fugam eripuit de ipsius manibus et viribus exivit, prout nobis relatum fuit, per dictum potentatem et per plures homines dicte terre...»].

Fig. 47 - «Ex defectu et culpa ipsius potentatis fugam eripuit...», from manuscript no. 40 preserved at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco (single folium, recto), as published in low resolution by Progetto Elissa, *Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.* (Montemonaco, 1998), p. 13

Let's try to figure out what happened. Poor Angelo, fearing he was lost and nearly ready for the stake, must have cried a lot, and wailed aloud a lot, and certainly paid a lot of money, handing over many of those shining pieces of gold to his wardens so as to buy his own deliverance. And the authorities in Montemonaco, not wishing for him the harrowing flames of the stake, must have thought it better not to disappoint so munificent a customer, and so dangerous a witness of their own guilt and interested connivance with foreign alchemists: and so just opened the jail's door, and let him go.

«... out of carelessness and guilt of that same local authority...», writes an astounded de Guardarijs.

And particularly humorous seems to us, today, the amazed remarks pronounced by the perplexed judge in his sentence, that «was not possible to us to understand who was the real perpetrator of the flight of the said Angelo, nor [...] could we ascertain the actual truth of the facts» (in the original Latin text: «ob quem causam et fugam ipsius domini Angeli principalis auctoris et [...] non potuimus examinare et perfectam rei veritatem invenire idcircho»): we can imagine, today, the blank, seemingly-unperturbed faces of the Priors and the representatives of the inhabitants of Montemonaco, who during the trial had told the judge they knew nothing about the whole matter, now listening to the puzzled words of the judge in a cold sweat.

They were surely thanking God because this time they had eluded punishment by a hair, in this thoroughly perilous predicament.

And they were now safe, at least until the next summer. When business would start over again.

Montemonaco made money with foreign morons. Locals liked it and wanted to keep business going.

For the time being, judge Christophorus de Guardarijs couldn't but feel helpless:

«And as it results to us and our court that all and each of the accusations contained in the said inquisition might be not true [...] We, Christophorus de Guardarijs, [...] judge with jurisdiction over spiritual cases, the said Priors, population, municipality and all the men in the land of Montemonaco we declare not guilty and release...».

[In the original Latin text: «Et quia constat nobis et nostre curie preditta omnia et singula contenta in superditta inquisitione non fuisse vera [...] Nos Christophorus de Guardarijs, [...] iudex in spiritualibus [...] predittos priores universitatem commune et homines terre Montis Monaci absolvimus et liberamus...».

Montemonaco was acquitted. Until another summer would come.

6. Reviewing our interpretation for consistency

We are now reaching the conclusion of our fascinating travel across fifteenth-century Montemonaco, a small hamlet sitting on the foot of Mount Sibyl, the famous Italian mountain that, at the time and also in subsequent centuries, was at the center of a mighty process of international attraction owing to the presence of eerie legendary tales concerning a sibilline Cave and a demonic Lake, the latter lying in the neighboring Mount Vettore.

As we know from a significant number of sources, available starting from the fourteenth century, people from various countries of Europe used to come to this remote area, lost amid the Apennine mountains in central Italy,

in search of magical experiences and a suitable stage for carrying out forbidden rituals: possibly, the remnants of a much more ancient mythical function performed by the two sites in connection to potential cults devoted to earthquakes, developed by men during the Iron Age owing to the peculiar seismic nature of this territory, as we conjectured in our previous paper *The chthonian legend* (2020).

In this framework, Montemonaco, a main access point to the two legendary sites of the Sibillini Mountain Range, was a primary element in the account written by Antoine de la Sale concerning his personal journey to Mount Sibyl, carried out in 1420. Montemonaco («ad montem Lumonacho...») was also mentioned by St. James of the Marches in his fifteenth-century *Sermones dominicales* as a place where people went to consult enchanters and even perform ghastly encounters with demons. Other references (Flavio Biondo, Felix Hemmerlin, Enea Silvio Piccolomini, Bernardino Bonavoglia) mentions Norcia, Montegallo and Montefortino, which are all settlements that lie not far from Montemonaco, and share with the latter the same proximity to the legends.

We then analysed the astounding trove made by Project Elissa and Anna Maria Piscitelli in Montemonaco in 1997: a manuscript dating to 1452 which contains a sentence of acquittal rendered by the justice of the Papal States in favor of the local authorities and people of Montemonaco, following accusations of having supported foreign «alchemists» wishing to access the Lake of the Sibyl («ad lacum Sibille») to perform forbidden rituals.

The document is a most significant confirmation of the mythical renown experienced by Mount Sibyl and Mount Vettore in the course of the fifteenth century, with a gloomy reputation featured by both sites across Europe within a milieu of men of letters, aristocrats, adventurers and would-be sorcerers and alchemists. The manuscript also confirms that the Papal States were fully aware of this peculiar, unwanted fame, and they made attempts at restraining the visits to the two sites by prosecuting the individuals who tried to reach the Cave and Lake, or were caught up there in suspicious attitude.

As we detailed in the previous paragraphs, Project Elissa tended to read the manuscript as an evidence of a widespread diffusion, among the inhabitants

of Montemonaco, of a magical, alchemical cultural background, rooted in an ancient shamanic knowledge that would allegedly have been living in the Sibillini Mountain Range since time immemorial.

We disagreed with this sort of interpretation, which we think mainly derives by that 'original sin' marking Project Elissa since its inception: the yearning for a supposed, unfounded, most-craved principle of 'Matriarchy', a generative force informing universe and life, following concepts expressed by hermeticist and alchemist Giuliano Kremmerz at the beginning of the twentieth century, then expanded by archaeologist Marija Gimbutas in the 1990s and finally ruinously and awkwardly applied to the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range by activist and writer Joyce Lussu.

In our opinion, a thorough perusal of manuscript no. 40 shows a different, and more reasonable, reality: though forbidden by the Church, the locals in Montemonaco thought it better to help and support all those strange visitors who used to flock to their small hamlet during each summer. Because they paid money. Actually, a lot of money.

Fig. 48 - Medieval coins

Like a religious, spiritual destination, a location which preserves the holy relics of a saint within an official shrine, used to attract crowds of pilgrims from many nations, with those pilgrims gladly willing to pay for food, accommodation and other services, Montemonaco welcomed its own peculiar travellers as well — though, of course, over much smaller numbers.

People came from abroad to visit the Lake of Pilate and/or the Sibyl's Cave, looking for a meeting with demonic entities or the admission to a subterranean kingdom of sensuality and lust. They came from foreign

countries, they knew all about the fairy tales but nothing about the real place, they did not even know where to sleep and eat and groom their horses. They needed guidance for almost everything: how to get to the Cave, how to reach the Lake, which trail was to be taken, whether guides may be hired.

All those people awaited for services to be offered and delivered to them: lodging, boarding, local guides.

Certainly enough, they were not as numerous as spiritual pilgrims. But often they came in groups, noblemen got there with their small retinue of friends and servants. And they all needed help and support.

And we must consider another aspects: maybe they weren't as numerous as pilgrims; but — let's think about it — with respect to pilgrims, they were much richer.

Because the individuals who came to Montemonaco to make their forbidden dreams come true were not miserable travellers: often they were well-to-do, wealthy aristocrats, who could afford a long, expensive travel through the Italian peninsula in search of a fairy-tale, a reverie, an illusion for men of letters, simpletons and alleged wizards.

They were rich and they could pay in golden and silver coins. So why shouldn't the locals have exploited this lucky chance? They had no relics of saints, but who cared?... They had the Sibyl!

That's why, as judge de Guardarijs noted in his sentence, «they accommodated and housed in the commune and provided support, advice and help» to those visitors; and they did it «scienter, deliberately, knowingly and with purposeful and intentional resolution». They «helped and supported» their foreign guests «as to their sustenance and provision»; they gave them «bread and wine and any other needed supply», and also «accompanied them up to the said lake of the Sibyl».

Money and services; services and money. We may suppose that in some beautiful summer days visitors were so many that the small hamlet might have experienced some difficulties in accommodating them all; so, possibly a large number of inhabitants of Montemonaco were involved in providing

services to them, as it appears from the words written by de Guardarijs: «certain people coming from the Kingdom of Naples and Spain were housed and accommodated in a house belonging to Mr. Catarino, of the said land, located in the same place...». For sure, smart Mr. Catarino, and many others, knew how to profit from this lodging activity.

Fig. 49 - An artistic vision of a possible lodging for the visitor's servants in a peasant's house in medieval Montemonaco

Let's point out an important aspect: business in Montemonaco did not imply any cheating. It was just a fair deliverance of services, even though possibly at high prices. In this respect we must also consider that, if the affluent foreigners really required fine lodging and boarding amid such remote mountains, where normally no services are to be found, they had to pay correspondingly for them.

We can also imagine the rich business carried out by the local inns and taverns, especially in the summer evenings, when the tired, excited visitors (who up there in altitude had been looking for strong emotions, including meeting with demons and paying lustful visits to the Sibyl) required the supply of streams of wine, barrels of beer and, perhaps, even lewder kinds of late-night services.

The whole village was involved in the business, directly or indirectly. And, sure enough, the whole thing was kept as confidential as they could, not to incur the rage of the Pope's constabulary and the General Curia «with jurisdiction over spiritual cases». The Priors, who should have reported the whole matter to the higher authorities and jurisdictions, were fully involved in the business and covered the entire affair in the hope never to be caught red-handed.

But rumors ran fast, and that year something went wrong. Someone, possibly out of resentment and sacred indignation, reported all that hustle and bustle to the Curia in Tolentino: «according to public rumours and following what was referred to us as an amazing voice, not arising from ill-intentioned or deceitful people but, on the contrary, by honest and trustworthy persons, and not in a single occasion but more than once, it came to our ears and to this spiritual jurisdiction...».

So a criminal trial was perilously established. The outcome could have been potentially ominous: the stake for some (including the Priors), and the excommunication for all the others.

But, in Montemonaco, they all were effectively prepared to this sort of worst case, when personal survival itself was at stake. And they acted as a single man, to save their own life and that of their families.

First, they promptly released the foreign alchemists that had been caught by the papal police and transferred into their custody. The foreigners just fled. Who knows how? Nobody knew. What a pity. No more dangerous witnesses around here. Sorry for that little inconvenience. Our apologies.

Secondly, they were forced to take part in the trial as defendants. But, they said, they knew absolutely nothing of all that fuss; they had lodged no foreign visitors; life in the hamlet had been going on, that summer, as had always been. And they all, *nemine contradicente*, stared at the judge with fully blank faces, as if in an astounded stupor.

In Montemonaco, they repeated, there were honest workers only, and conscientious Christians. They did know nothing about those silly legends on lakes, caves and demons, and they did not even want to know.

And in the end judge de Guardarijs could only write, in his sentence, that «we could not ascertain the actual truth of the facts» («non potuimus [...] perfectam rei veritatem invenire»). So «the said Priors, population, municipality and all the men in the land of Montemonaco we declare not guilty and release...».

So in 1452 Montemonaco, its Priors and its inhabitants succeeded in shunning all punishments. Even though the justice of the Papal States had made an attempt at prosecuting them, their guilt could not be proven, and facts could not be ascertained.

And all we wrote here, though certainly to be considered as a tentative interpretation of the content of manuscript no. 40, seems to provide full consistency with what is actually written on that remarkable, unique parchment folium.

Fig. 50 - «In Dei nomine. Amen», the introductory invocation from manuscript no. 40 preserved at the Historical Archive of Montemonaco (single folium, recto), as published in low resolution by Progetto Elissa, *Sulle tracce della Sibilla - Un documento del XV sec.* (Montemonaco, 1998), p. 13

7. *Our interpretation corroborated by Antoine de la Sale*

So we reckon that our surmise on what has been going on in Montemonaco in year 1452 is not far from truth.

And we think that a further, illustrious confirmation of this same surmise is provided to us by a prominent protagonist of the sibilline lore: Antoine de la Sale.

In his *The paradise of Queen Sibyl* we find a stunningly accurate pictorial representation of the typical assistance provided by the inhabitants of Montemonaco to one of those distinct visitors, i.e. Antoine de la Sale himself.

You may remember that at the beginning of the present article we recalled the following words written by de la Sale:

«I went there [to the Sibyl's Cave, editor's note] with a doctor of the said village, whose name was John of Sore; he led me there, together with other people of the hamlet of Montemonaco who escorted us up there».

[In the original French text: «j'etoie la alé avec un docteur dudit pais, nommé messire Jehan de Sore qui me conduisoit, et les gens de la ville de Montemoynaco qui nous guidoient jusques la»].

We also mentioned the words that Antoine de la Sale wrote in the very opening of his *The paradise of Queen Sibyl*, a further testimony to the active role played by the inhabitants of Montemonaco in the management of foreign visitors and the diffusion of the legendary material:

«... my most illustrious dame, I send to you in writing and in portrait the mountain of the lake of Pilate and of the Sibyl [...] and also all I could see and get as information from the people living in that land...».

[In the original French text: «... ma tresredoubtee dame, vous envoie par escript et pourtrait le mons du lac de Pilate et de la Sibille [...] et aussi tout ce que je ay peu veoir et moy informer par les gens du pais...»].

And the miniature contained in folium 9v of his most famous manuscript just illustrates what used to happen by the dark entrance to the Sibyl's Cave: we see Antoine de la Sale entering the Cave's hollow backwards, assisted by the people of Montemonaco, handing the lanterns over to him and carrying supplies and provisions.

Fig. 51 - Antoine de la Sale accompanied by the inhabitants of Montemonaco to the Sibyl's Cave, from his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 9v)

So it's actual truth. The locals gladly accompanied the foreign visitors up to the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate.

And why did they do all this so gladly? The reason, in our opinion, is easily understood: because of money.

As all his fellow-visitors coming from distant countries, Antoine de la Sale, too, had to pay his fees to the people in Montemonaco to have a guide up to the Cave, be supplied with the appropriate provisions, and get boarding and

overnight accommodation at the village. All that implied the payment of most welcome money to the residents.

Valuable cash in exchange for services was so welcome that the locals did not restrain from entertaining Antoine, while ascending the steep mountainside to the renowned eerie spot, with a number of thrilling, hair-raising folk tales concerning the many people who had dared enter the Cave and found a wondrous scenario: the supernatural wind, the magical bridge, the crushing doors, and, finally, the court of the Sibyl...:

«... what the people of the land and the said town [Montemonaco, editor's note] told me about that. Some make fun of it, some others give credit to it out of the ancient popular tales».

[In the original French text: «... ce que les gens du pais et de ladicte ville m'en ont dit. Les uns s'en moquent, et les autres y adjoustent grant foy par l'ancien parler de la commune gent»].

Fig. 52 - The people of Montemonaco tell Antoine de la Sale the fascinating tales on the Sibyl's Cave, from his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 10r)

Furthermore, the locals liked foreigners' money so much that they also indulged in 'inventing', on the very spot, picturesque tableaux to the benefit of the excited visitors, as the circumstances consented:

«They and I myself heard a high voice that was screaming as if it were the cry of a peacock, and which seemed to come from far away. People there said that it was a voice arising from the paradise of the Sibyl. Yet, in my

opinion, I don't believe at all, instead I think they were my own horses that were waiting at the foot of the mountain, even though they were far down there and very distant from me».

[In the original French text: «Iceulx et moy oysmes leans une haulte voix criant ainsi que ce feust le cry du paon, qui sembloit estre moult loings. Si dirent les gens que c'estoit une voix de paradis de la Sibille; mais, quant a moy, je n'en croy riens, ains croy que feussent mes chevaux qui au pié du mont estoient, combien qu'ilz feussent moult bas et loings de moi»].

Fig. 53 - Antoine de la Sale's local guides magnify the evocative character of Mount Sibyl by adding further picturesque notes, from his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 9v and 10r)

In the fifteenth century, just like today, tourists asked to be entertained and amused.

And in past times, just like today, tourists had to pay to get entertained. Because, as everybody knows, business is business.

8. *Business and beyond*

The facts that occurred in Montemonaco in 1452, it seems to us, did not hint to any penchant of the residents towards forbidden magical and alchemical practices; instead, in a practical, almost professional way, the locals preferred to earn money from exploiting the plethora of wealthy morons that used to come from abroad: those visitors dreamed of blood-curdling encounters with ghosts, demons and fairy tales, and gladly wanted to pay for making their dream come true.

For the locals, it was just business. And yet not completely so.

Because all this does not mean that people in Montemonaco did not believe at all in the legendary tales which inhabited their territory.

They knew their legends and they respected them. Tales about fairies and demons and sibilline damsels fully circulated among them too, as Antoine de la Sale himself reports («some make fun of it, some others give credit to it out of the ancient popular tales»); and they knew well the sense of awe that the sinister waters of the Lake of Pilate or the gloomy entrance to the Sibyl's Cave induced in their hearts.

Who could know what was mere legend, and what was instead actual, terrifying, otherworldly truth?

We must remember that, according to the conjecture we outlined in our paper *The chthonian legend* (2020), possibly in a remote antiquity this land had represented for men a sort of otherworldly point of access: a place where to establish an eerie communication with the chthonian potencies that presided over earthquakes; two highland shrines, at the Lake and by the Cave, for the performance of rituals in a view to appease the seismic waves, as demonic and frightful in the Iron Age as they are today. In our conjecture, the possible ancient existence of this cult might have implied a sort of latency of the associated mythical material, which has gone subsequently lost but has possibly maintained its dreary mark on the peaks and cliffs of the Sibillini Mountain Range, attracting in the centuries of the Middle Ages new legendary layers coming from abroad and concerning sibilline oracles and Roman prefects.

Fig. 54 - The Lake of Pilate at sunset

All this means that the people residing at the foot of Mount Sibyl and Mount Vettore, recursively struck by godlike earthquakes, enshrouded in the faint, misty remnants of most antique cults, immersed in the radiance of the hidden realm of an oracular, sensual Sibyl, frightened by the demonic presence concealed under the icy waters of a Lake of Pilate, they all lived encircled by mythical, mysterious, emotional vibrations, which rendered them sensitive to the spell of the place, and not callously indifferent to the fairy tales and narratives that lived in their own territory.

So we can imagine, in accord with Project Elissa, that a few of the inhabitants of Montemonaco may have practiced alchemy or sorcery or even the summoning of malicious entities, also offering some qualified guidance to foreign visitors. But they were only individuals. The «population, municipality and all the men in the land of Montemonaco» just lived their own lives, welcomed visitors in summers, and looked at the high cliffs of Mount Sibyl and Mount Vettore, clothed in legends, with concern and awe.

Fig. 55 - Mount Sibyl at sunset

All that said, visitors coming in the good season were not fairies, but real human beings with their pockets full of valuable coins. So profiting from such a favourable situation was certainly on top of the residents' priorities, just like other local residents used to do in most renowned spiritual sites across Italy and Europe which used to attract pilgrims and wayfarers, like Rome or Santiago de Compostela; or even like Cumae in southern Italy and Lough Dergh in Ireland, where other ghastly Otherworlds opened their dark jaws for living men to enter (as we fully illustrated in our previous paper *Sibillini Mountain Range, a Cave and a Lake to the Otherworld*, 2020).

Good deals and spine-tingling stories. That was the mix in Montemonaco in 1452.

And it was a profitable, emotional, exciting mix.

9. Conclusive remarks

In the present paper we illustrated our interpretation of manuscript no. 40, as found by Project Elissa in the Historical Archive of the municipality of Montemonaco.

We intended to stay away from interpretative visions which appear to be far too excessive in terms of envisaged adherence of an entire population to esoteric and philosophical doctrines which normally are the field of study of a limited number of happy few, and certainly are not endorsed by the majority of normal people, living and working in a small town set at the foot of remote mountains, though in medieval years.

In perusing manuscript no. 40 for the first time, we found that the interpretation provided by Project Elissa was too dramatic, too serious, too heavily drawn to depict the true reality of the conditions to be encountered in Montemonaco in 1452. We consider as naively designed, and even marked by some sort of wishful thinking, a vision which portrays the residents as fully interested in alchemy or sorcery, in agreement with visitors coming from outside. Instead, a simpler explanation of the facts narrated in manuscript no. 40 can be easily based on money, business, and the delivery of 'touristic' services to foreigners which were carrying special interests with them, but with no mandatory adherence to such interests on the part of the locals.

We think that a new reading of the manuscript's text in the light of what we have highlighted in the present paper may prove to be more productive in terms of effectiveness of the historical analysis, and illuminate the real meaning of facts and events.

«We could not ascertain the actual truth of the facts» («non potuimus [...] perfectam rei veritatem invenire»), wrote judge de Guardarijs in his

sentence. But we hope we could shed a new light upon those same facts, six hundred years after they took place.

And we hope, with our article, to have contributed to a better understanding of the astounding, illustrious history of the charming small town of Montemonaco, sitting on its hill just in front, and at the very presence, of the celebrated Queen of these mountains: the Sibyl of the Apennines.

Fig. 56 - Montemonaco and the crowned shape of Mount Sibyl (top left)

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